

MCMULE

The MCMULE manual

THE MCMULE TEAM

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MCMULE is a generic framework for higher-order QED calculations of scattering and decay processes involving leptons. In this note we describe all relevant details of the implementation and provide very detailed instructions for running and analysing with MCMULE.

Author's note: please also refer to the official MCMULE publication [1] as well as the doctoral thesis it is based on [2] for detailed background information. Please cite this document as

```
@article{McMule2022:manual,  
  Title = "{The_{\sc McMule}_Manual}",  
  Author = "Ulrich, Yannick and others",  
  url = "https://mule-tools.gitlab.io/manual",  
  doi = "10.5281/zenodo.6046769",  
  Year = "2022"  
}
```

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process	order	experiments	comments	status
$\mu \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} e$	NNLO	MEG I&II	polarised, massified & exact	[5]
$\mu \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} e \gamma$	NLO	MEG I	polarised	[6]
$\mu \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} e e e$	NLO	Mu3e	polarised	[7]
$\mu \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} e \gamma \gamma$	LO	MEG	polarised	priv. comm.
$\tau \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} e \gamma$	NLO	BaBar	cuts in lab frame	[6]
$\tau \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} l l l$	NLO	Belle II		*
$e \mu \rightarrow e \mu$	NLO	MUonE		complete
	NNLO		purely electronic corrections	[1]
			mixed (massified)	†
$\ell p \rightarrow \ell p$	NNLO	P2, MUSE, Prad	only leptonic corrections	complete
$e^- e^- \rightarrow e^- e^-$	NNLO	Prad	complete	[8]
$e^+ e^- \rightarrow e^+ e^-$	NNLO		no n_f	[9]
$e^+ e^- \rightarrow \gamma \gamma$	NNLO	PADME		*
$e^+ e^- \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$	NNLO	Belle	massified	†

Table 1: A list of processes that are either already included in MCMULE, almost implemented (*), or planned to be implemented (†).

MCMULE (**M**onte **c**arlo for **M**uons and other **l**eptons) is a generic framework for higher-order QED calculations of scattering and decay processes involving leptons. It is written in Fortran 95 with two types of users in mind. First, several processes are implemented, some at NLO, some at NNLO. For these processes, the user can define an arbitrary (infrared safe), fully differential observable and compute cross sections and distributions. MCMULE's processes, present and future, are listed in Table 1 together with the relevant experiments for which the cuts are implemented. Second, the program is set up s.t. additional processes can be implemented by supplying the relevant matrix elements.

The public version of the code can be found at

<https://gitlab.com/mule-tools/mcmule>

An internal version can be found at

<https://gitlab.com/mule-tools/monte-carlo>

Access to the latter will be granted by the MCMULE core team (MMCT), usually for new collaborators who wish to extend MCMULE in meaningful ways.

To obtain a copy of the code, `git` is recommended

```
$ git clone --recursive https://gitlab.com/mule-tools/mcmule
```

Alternatively, we provide a Docker container [3] for easy deployment and legacy results (cf. Section 5.5). In multi-user environments, `udocker` [4] can be used instead. In either case, a pre-compiled copy of the code can be obtained by calling

```
$ docker pull yulrich/mcmule # requires Docker to be installed
$ udocker pull yulrich/mcmule # requires udocker to be installed
```

We provide instructions on how MCMULE is used in Section 2.

1 Structure of MCMULE

MCMULE is written in Fortran 95 with helper and analysis tools written in `python`³. The code is written with two kinds of applications in mind. First, several processes are implemented, some at NLO, some at NNLO. For these, the user can define an arbitrary (infrared safe), fully differential observable and compute cross sections and distributions. Second, the program is set up such that additional processes can be implemented by supplying the relevant matrix elements.

To obtain a copy of MCMULE we recommend the following approach

```
$ git clone --recursive https://gitlab.com/mule-tools/mcmule
```

To build MCMULE, a Fortran compiler such as `gfortran` and a `python` installation is needed. The main executable can be compiled by running

```
$ ./configure
$ make
```

Alternatively, we provide a Docker container [3] for easy deployment and legacy results (cf. Section 5.5). In multi-user environments, `udocker` [4] can be used instead. In either case, a pre-compiled copy of the code can be obtained by calling

```
$ docker pull yulrich/mcmule # requires Docker to be installed
$ udocker pull yulrich/mcmule # requires uDocker to be installed
```

We provide instructions on how MCMULE is used in Section 2.

When started, `mcmule` reads options from `stdin` as specified in Table 4 (cf. Section 2). The value and error estimate of the integration is printed to `stdout` and the full status of the integration is written in a machine-readable format into a folder called `out/` (see below).

MCMULE consists of several modules with a simple, mostly hierarchic structure. The relation between the most important Fortran modules is depicted in Figure 2. A solid arrow indicates “using” the full module, whereas a dashed arrow is indicative of partial use. In what follows we give a brief description of the various modules and mention some variables that play a prominent role in the interplay between the modules.

global_def: This module simply provides some parameters such as fermion masses that are needed throughout the code. It also defines `prec` as a generic type for the precision used.⁴ Currently, this simply corresponds to double precision.

functions: This module is a library of basic functions that are needed at various points in the code. This includes dot products, eikonal factors, the integrated eikonal, and an interface for scalar integral functions among others.

collier: This is an external module [10–13]. It will be linked to MCMULE during compilation and provides the numerical evaluations of the scalar and in some cases tensor integral functions in `functions`.

phase_space: The routines for generating phase-space points and their weights are collected in this module. Phase-space routines ending with `FKS` are prepared for the `FKS` subtraction

³Additionally to the `python` tool a `Mathematica` tool is available.

⁴For quad precision `prec=16` and the compiler flag `-fdefault-real-16` is required.

Figure 2: The structure of MCMULE.

procedure with a single unresolved photon. In the weight of such routines a factor ξ_1 is omitted to allow the implementation of the distributions in the FKS method. This corresponds to a global variable `xiout1`. This factor has to be included in the integrand of the module `integrand`s. Also the variable `ksoft1` is provided that corresponds to the photon momentum without the (vanishing) energy factor ξ_1 . Routines ending with `FKSS` are routines with two unresolved photons. Correspondingly, a factor $\xi_1 \xi_2$ is missing in the weight and `xiout1` and `xiout2`, as well as `ksoft1` and `ksoft2` are provided. To ensure numerical stability it is often required to tune the phase-space routine to a particular kinematic situation.

openloops: This is the external OpenLoops library [14, 15] that we use for some real-virtual matrix elements. It is pulled as a `git` submodule and linked to MCMULE during compilation.

olinterface: This connects `openloops` to the rest of MCMULE by initialising OpenLoops for the process under consideration and converting to and from the OpenLoops conventions which are slightly different than the ones used by MCMULE.

{pg}_mat_el : Matrix elements are grouped into process groups such as muon decay (`mudec`) or μ - e and μ - p scattering (`mue`). Each process group contains a `mat_el` module that provides all matrix elements for its group. Simple matrix elements are coded directly in this module. More complicated results are imported from sub-modules not shown in Figure 2. A matrix element starting with `P` contains a polarised initial state. A matrix element ending in `av` is averaged over a neutrino pair in the final state.

{pg}: In this module the soft limits of all applicable matrix elements of a process group are provided to allow for the soft subtractions required in the FKS scheme. These limits are simply the eikonal factor evaluated with `ksoft` from `phase_space` times the reduced matrix element, provided through `mat_el`.

This module also functions as the interface of the process group, exposing all necessary functions that are imported by

`mat_el`, which collects all matrix elements as well as their particle labelling or particle identification (PID).

user: For a user of the code who wants to run for an already implemented process, this is the only relevant module. At the beginning of the module, the user has to specify the number of quantities to be computed, `nr_q`, the number of bins in the histogram, `nr_bins`, as well as their lower and upper boundaries, `min_val` and `max_val`. The last three quantities are arrays of length `nr_q`. The quantities themselves, i.e. the measurement function, is to be defined by the user in terms of the momenta of the particles in `quant`. Cuts can be applied by setting the logical variable `pass_cut` to `false`⁵. Some auxiliary functions like (pseudo)rapidity, transverse momentum etc. are predefined in `functions`. Each quantity has to be given a name through the array `names`.

⁵Technically, `pass_cut` is a list of length `nr_q`, allowing to decide whether to cut for each histogram separately.

Further, `user` contains a subroutine called `inituser`. This allows the user to read additional input at runtime, for example which of multiple cuts should be calculated. It also allows the user to print some information on the configuration implemented. Needless to say that it is good idea to do this for documentation purposes.

vegas: As the name suggests this module contains the adaptive Monte Carlo routine `vegas` [16].

The binning routine `bin_it` is also in this module, hence the need for the binning metadata, i.e. the number of bins and histograms (`nr_bins` and `nr_q`, respectively) as well as their bounds (`min_val` and `max_val`) and names, from `user`.

integrands: In this module the functions that are to be integrated by `vegas` are coded. There are three types of integrands: non-subtracted, single-subtracted, and double-subtracted integrands, corresponding to the three parts of the FKS² scheme [2, 5]. The matrix elements to be evaluated and the phase-space routines used are set using function pointers through a subroutine `initpiece`. The factors ξ_i that were omitted in the phase-space weight have to be included here for the single- and double-subtracted integrands.

mcmule: This is the main program, but actually does little else than read the inputs and call `vegas` with a function provided by `integrands`.

test: For developing purposes, a separate main program exists that is used to validate the code after each change. Reference values for matrix elements and results of short integrations are stored here and compared against.

The library of matrix elements deserves a few comments. As matrix elements quickly become very large, we store them separately from the main code. This makes it also easy to extend the program by minimising the code that needs to be changed.

We group matrix elements into process groups, generic processes, and generic pieces as indicated in Appendix B. The generic process is a prototype for the physical process such as $\ell p \rightarrow \ell p$ where the flavour of the lepton ℓ is left open. The generic piece describes a part of the calculation such as the real or virtual corrections, i.e. the different pieces of (20) (or correspondingly (24) at NNLO), that themselves may be further subdivided as is convenient. In particular, in some cases a generic piece is split into various partitions (cf. Section 5.1 for details on why that is important).

When running `mcmule`, the code generates a statefile from which the full state of the integrator can be reconstructed should the integration be interrupted (cf. Section 5.4 for details). This makes the statefile ideal to also store results in a compact format. To analyse these results, we provide a python tool `pymule`, additionally to the main code for MCMULE. `pymule` uses `numpy` [17] for data storage and `matplotlib` for plotting [18]. While `pymule` works with any python interpreter, `IPython` [19] is recommended. We will encounter `pymule` in Section 3 when we discuss how to use it to analyse results. A full list of functions provided can be found in Appendix D.

2 Running MCMULE: an example

In order to provide a simple example with concrete instructions on how to run the code and to illustrate how it works, we consider the radiative decay of the tau $\tau \rightarrow [\nu\bar{\nu}]e\gamma$. Since the

neutrinos are not detected, we average over them, indicated by the brackets. Hence, we have to be fully inclusive w.r.t. the neutrinos. Still, the code allows to make any cut on the other final-state particles. As we will see, the BR for this process, as measured by BABAR [20, 21] has a discrepancy of more than 3σ from the SM value. This will illustrate the importance of fully differential NLO corrections in QED.

2.1 Preparations

To be concrete let us assume that we want to compute two distributions, the invariant mass of the $e\gamma$ pair, $m_{\gamma e} \equiv \sqrt{(p_e + p_\gamma)^2}$, and the energy of the electron, E_e , in the rest frame of the tau. To avoid an IR singularity in the BR, we have to require a minimum energy of the photon. We choose this to be $E_\gamma \geq 10$ MeV as used in [20, 21].

As mentioned in Section 1 the quantities are defined in the module `user` (`src/user.f95`). At the beginning of the module we set

```
nr_q = 2
nr_bins = 90
min_val = (/ 0._prec, 0._prec /)
max_val = (/ 1800._prec, 900._prec /)
```

where we have decided to have 90 bins for both distributions and `nr_q` determines the number of distributions. The boundaries for the distributions are set as $0 < m_{\gamma e} < 1800$ MeV and $0 \leq E_e \leq 900$ MeV.

The quantities themselves are defined in the function `quant` of the module `user`. This function takes arguments, `q1` to `q7`. These are the momenta of the particles, arrays of length 4 with the fourth entry the energy. Depending on the process though not all momenta are needed and may be zero.

The PID, i.e. which momentum corresponds to which particle, can be looked up in Appendix C as well as the file `mat_e1.f95`. In our case we find

```
use mudec, only: pm2ennngav!!(q1,n,q2,q3,q4,q5, linear)
!! mu+(p1) -> e+(p2) y(q5) + ( \nu_e \bar{\nu}_\mu )
!! mu-(p1) -> e-(p2) y(q5) + ( \bar{\nu}_e \nu_\mu )
!! for massive electron
!! average over neutrino tensor taken
```

This means that we have to use `q1` for the incoming τ , `q2` for the outgoing e , and `q5` for the outgoing γ . At NLO, we will also need `q6` for the second γ .

```
use mudec, only: pm2ennngav!!(p1, n1, p2, p3, p4, p5, p6)
!! mu+(p1) -> e+(p2) \nu_e \bar{\nu}_\mu g(p5) g(p6)
!! mu-(p1) -> e-(p2) \bar{\nu}_e \nu_\mu g(p5) g(p6)
!! for massive (and massless) electron
!! average over neutrino tensor taken
```

The momenta of the neutrinos do not enter, as we average over them.

Schematically, the function `quant` is shown in Listing 3. Here we have used `sq` provided by `functions` to compute the square of a four-vector. We have also specified the polarisation vector `pol1` s.t. the initial tau is considered unpolarised. The variable `pass_cut` controls the cuts. Initially it is set to true, to indicate that the event is kept. Applying a cut amounts to setting

```

FUNCTION QUANT(Q1,Q2,Q3,Q4,Q5,Q6,Q7)
...
pass_cut = .true.

if(q5(4) < 10._prec) pass_cut = .false.
pol1 = (/ 0._prec, 0._prec, 0._prec, 0._prec /)

names(1) = 'minv'
quant(1) = sqrt(sq(q2+q5))

names(2) = 'Ee'
quant(2) = q2(4)

END FUNCTION QUANT

```

Listing 3: An example for the function `quant` to calculate the radiative τ decay. Note that this is only valid at LO and should not be used in any actual calculation.

`pass_cut` to false. The version of `quant` in Listing 3 will work for a LO calculation, but will need to be adapted for the presence of a second photon in an NLO computation. Being content with LO for the moment, all that remains to be done is prepare the input read by `mcmule` from `stdin`, as specified in Table 4.

To be concrete let us assume we want to use 10 iterations with 1000×10^3 points each for pre-conditioning and 50 iterations with 1000×10^3 points each for the actual numerical evaluation (cf. Section 4.1 for some heuristics to determine the statistics needed). We pick a random seed between 0 and $2^{31} - 1$ (cf. Section 5.3), say 70 998, and for the input variable `which_piece` we enter `m2ennng0`. This stands for the generic process $\mu \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} e \gamma$ and 0 for tree level. The `flavour` variable is now set to `tau-e` to change from the generic process $\mu \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} e \gamma$ to the process we are actually interested in, $\tau \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} e \gamma$. This system is used for other processes as well. The input variable `which_piece` determines the generic process and the part of it that is to be computed

Variable name	Data type	Comment
<code>nenter_ad</code>	integer	calls / iteration during pre-conditioning
<code>itmx_ad</code>	integer	iterations during pre-conditioning
<code>nenter</code>	integer	calls / iteration during main run
<code>itmx</code>	integer	iterations during main run
<code>ran_seed</code>	integer	random seed z_1
<code>xinormcut</code>	real(prec)	the $0 < \xi_c \leq 1$ parameter
<code>delcut</code>	real(prec)	the δ_{cut} parameter (or at NNLO the second ξ_c)
<code>which_piece</code>	char(10)	the part of the calculation to perform
<code>flavour</code>	char(8)	the particles involved
<code>(opt)</code>	unknown	the user can request further input during <code>userinit</code>

Table 4: The options read from `stdin` by `MCMULE`

```

$ ./mcmule
1000
10
10000
50
70998
1.0
1.0
m2enng0
tau-e
$ ./mcmule < b1.in
$ echo "1000\n10\n10000\n50\n70998\n1.0\n1.0\nm2enng0\ntau-e" \
| ./mcmule

```

Listing 5: Methods to enter configuration into MCMULE. All four invocations will result in the same run assuming the text file `r1.in` contains the correct data.

(i.e. tree level, real, double virtual etc.). In a second step, the input `flavour` associates actual numbers to the parameters entering the matrix elements and phase-space generation.

Obviously, in practice the input will typically not be given by typing in by hand. In Listing 5, we have listed four equivalent ways to input this data into `mcmule`. The two variables `xinormcut1` and `xinormcut2` have no effect at all for a tree-level calculation and will be discussed below in the context of the NLO run. We also ignore the optional input for the moment.

Now the mule is ready to trot. The first step it does in `mcmule` is to associate the numerical values of the masses, as specified through `flavour`. In particular, we set the generic masses `Mm` and `Me` to `Mtau` and `Me1`. This is done in `initflavour`, defined in `global_def`. For other processes this might also involve setting e.g. centre-of-mass energies `scms` to default values.

Next, the function to be integrated by `vegas` is determined. This is a function stored in `integrands`. There are basically three types of integrands: a standard, non-subtracted integrand, `sigma_0`, a single-subtracted integrand needed beyond LO, `sigma_1`, and a double-subtracted integrand needed beyond NLO, `sigma_2`. Which integrand is needed and what matrix elements and phase-space it depends on is determined by calling the function `init_piece` which uses the variable `which_piece` to point function pointers at the necessary procedures. For our LO case, `init_piece` sets the integrand to `sigma_0` and fixes the dimension of the integration to `ndim = 8`. The matrix element pointer is assigned to the matrix element that needs to be called, `Pm2enngAV(q1,n1,q2,q3,q4,q5)`. The name of the function suggests we compute $\mu(q_1, n_1) \rightarrow [\nu(q_3)\bar{\nu}(q_4)]e(q_2)\gamma(q_5)$ with the polarisation vector `n1` of the initial lepton. Even though we average over the neutrinos, their momenta are still given for completeness.

The interplay between the function `sigma_0(x,wgt,ndim)` and `vegas` is as usual, through an array of random numbers `x` of length `ndim` that corresponds to the dimension of the integration. In addition there is the `vegas` weight of the event, `wgt` due to the Jacobian introduced by the importance sampling. The function `sigma_0` simply evaluates the complete weight `wg` of a particular event by combining `wgt` with the matrix element supplemented by symmetry, flux, and phase-space factors. In a first step a phase-space routine of `phase_space` is called. For our LO calculation, `init_piece` pointed a pointer to the phase-space routine `psd5_25(x, p1,Mm, p2,Me, p3,0., p4,0., p5,0., wght)`, a phase-space routine optimised for radiative lepton

decays (cf. Section 5.1). This will be called as a first step in the integrand to generate the momenta with correct masses as well as the phase-space weight `weight`. With these momenta the observables to be computed are evaluated with a call to `quant`. If one of them passes the cuts, the variable `cuts` is set to true. This triggers the computation of the matrix element and the assembly of the full weight. In a last step, the routine `bin_it`, stored in `vegas`, is called to put the weight into the correct bins of the various distributions. If the variable under- or overshoots the bounds specified by `min_val` and `max_val`, the event is placed into dedicated, infinitely big under- and overflow bins. These steps are done for all events and those after pre-conditioning are used to obtain the final distributions.

For a corresponding computation at NLO, a few things need to be modified. First, the observables have to be specified more carefully. In particular, we need to decide how we treat the additional photon due to real radiation. In our example we will consider the exclusive radiative decay, i.e. we request precisely one photon with energy $E_\gamma > 10$ MeV. The function `quant` will have to take this into account with the additional argument `q6`, the momentum of the second photon.

An example of how this could be done is shown in Listing 6. Here we have just defined the harder and softer photon `gah` and `gas`, respectively, and require that the former (latter) has energy larger (smaller) than 10 MeV. This version of `quant` is also suitable for the LO calculation, and to ensure infrared-safety, it is generally advisable to use a single `quant` function for all parts of a computation. This is also mandatory if LO and NLO runs are done in one go, as discussed below.

With this version of `quant` we evaluate the virtual and real corrections, as well as the infrared counterterm (i.e. the integrated eikonal times the tree-level matrix element.) The latter is often combined with the virtual corrections. The corresponding `which_piece` are `m2enngV`, `m2enngR`, and `m2enngC`, respectively. If the counterterm is combined with the virtual part, we would use `m2enngF` which is not implemented.

2.2 Running MCMULE natively

When we run MCMULE, we will want to choose various random seeds and different values for the unphysical parameter ξ_c . Checking the independence of physical results on the latter serves as a consistency check. To do this, it helps to disentangle `m2enngF` into `m2enngV` and `m2enngC`. Only the latter depends on ξ_c and this part is typically much faster in the numerical evaluation. However, this can quickly lead to a rather large number of runs that need to be taken care of.

A particularly convenient way to run MCMULE is using menu files⁶. A menu file contains a list of jobs to be computed s.t. the user will only have to vary the random seed and ξ_c by hand as the statistical requirements are defined globally in a config file. This is completed by a submission script, usually called `submit.sh`. The submit script is what will need to be launched. It will take care of the starting of different jobs. It can be run on a normal computer or on a Slurm cluster [22].

To prepare the run in this way we can use `pymule` as shown in Listing 7. When using the tool, we are asked various questions, most of which have a default answer in square brackets. In the end `pymule` will create a directory that the user decided to call `babar-tau-e`, where all

⁶The name menu was originally used by the cryptanalysts at Bletchley Park to describe a particular set of configurations for the ‘computer’ to try

```

FUNCTION QUANT(Q1,Q2,Q3,Q4,Q5,Q6,Q7)
...
  pass_cut = .true.

  qq5 = 0._prec
  qq6 = 0._prec
  if(present(q5)) qq5=q5
  if(present(q6)) qq6=q6

  if (qq5(4) > qq6(4)) then
    gah = qq5 ; gas = qq6
  else
    gah = qq6 ; gas = qq5
  endif

  if (gah(4) < 10.) pass_cut = .false.
  if (gas(4) > 10.) pass_cut = .false.

names(1) = 'minv'
quant(1) = sqrt(sq(q2+gah))

names(2) = 'Ee'
quant(2) = q2(4)

END FUNCTION QUANT

```

Listing 6: An example for the function `quant` to calculate the radiative τ decay at NLO. This implementation is IR safe and exclusive w.r.t. extra photons.

results will be stored. The menu and config files generated by `pymule` are shown in Figure 8

To start `mcmule`, we now just need to execute the created `babar-tau-e/submit.sh`. Note that per default this will spawn at most as many jobs as the computer `pymule` ran on had CPU cores. If the user wishes a different number of parallel jobs, change the fifth line of `babar-tau-e/submit.sh` to

```
#SBATCH --ntasks=<number of cores>
```

2.3 Running MCMULE as a container

Linux containers are an emergent new technology in the software engineering world. The main idea behind such containerisation is to bundle all dependencies with a software when shipping. This allows the software to be executed regardless of the Linux distribution running on the host system without having to install any software beyond the containerising tool. This is possible without any measurable loss in performance. For these reasons, containerising MCMULE allows the code to be easily deployed on any modern computer, including systems running macOS or Windows (albeit with a loss of performance), and all results to be perfectly reproducible.

A popular containerisation tool is Docker [3]. Unfortunately, Docker requires some processes to be executed in privileged mode which is rarely available in the multi-user environments usually found on computing infrastructures. This led to the creation of `udocker` [4] which circumvents these problems. `udocker` can be obtained from

<https://github.com/indigo-dc/udocker>

`udocker` can be installed by calling ⁷

```
$ curl https://raw.githubusercontent.com/indigo-dc/udocker/master/  
  ↪ udocker.py > udocker  
$ chmod u+rx ./udocker  
$ ./udocker install
```

Once Docker or `udocker` has been installed, MCMULE can be downloaded by simply calling

```
$ docker pull yulrich/mcmule # requires Docker to be installed  
$ udocker pull yulrich/mcmule # requires udocker to be installed
```

This automatically fetches the latest public release of MCMULE deemed stable by the MMCT. We will discuss some technical details behind containerisation in Section 5.5.

MCMULE can be run containerised on a specified `user.f95` which is compiled automatically into `mcmule`. This is possible both directly or using menu files as discussed above. To run MCMULE directly on a specified `user.f95`, simply call

```
$ ./tools/run-docker.sh -i yulrich/mcmule:latest -u path/to/user.  
  ↪ f95 -r
```

This requests the same input already discussed in Table 4 and Listing 5. To run a containerised menu file, add an `image` command before the first `conf` command in the menu file

⁷It might be advisable to point the variable `UDOCKER_DIR` to a folder on a drive without quota first as `udocker` requires sizeable disk space

```

$ python -m pymule create -i # Use this if pymule is not installed
..
$ python pymule create -i # Use this if pymule is installed
What generic process? [m2enn] m2enng
Which flavour combination? [mu-e] tau-e
How many / which seeds? [5]
Which xi cuts? [[0.5, 0.25, 0.125]]
Where to store data? [m2enngtau-e] babar-tau-e
Which pieces? [['0', 'V', 'R']] 0, V, C, R
How much statistics for 0 (pc, pi, c, i)? [(10000, 20, 100000, 100)]
    ↪ 1000,10,1000,50
How much statistics for V (pc, pi, c, i)? [(10000, 20, 100000, 100)]
    ↪ 1000,10,1000,50
How much statistics for C (pc, pi, c, i)? [(10000, 20, 100000, 100)]
    ↪ 1000,10,1000,50
How much statistics for R (pc, pi, c, i)? [(10000, 20, 100000, 100)]
    ↪ 5000,50,10000,100
Building files. To rerun this, execute
python pymule create\
    --seeds 70998 66707 69184 75845 63937 \
    -xi 0.5 0.25 0.125 \
    --flavour tau-e \
    --genprocess m2enng \
    --output-dir babar-tau-e \
    --prog mcmule \
    --stat R,5000,50,10000,100 \
    --stat 0,1000,10,1000,50 \
    --stat V,1000,10,1000,50 \
    --stat C,1000,10,1000,50
Expect 3750 iterations, 20.250000G calls
Created menu, config and submit script in babar-tau-e
Please change the ntasks and time options accordingly

```

Listing 7: The steps necessary to use pymule to prepare running MCMULE. Input by the user is shown in bold. A red arrow indicates a graphical line wrap. Note that numbers listed as seeds are random and hence not reproducible.

```
## Generated at 16:00 on February 28 2020 by yannickulrich
# git version: redesign (b558978)
```

```
conf babar-tau-e/m2enng-tau-e.conf

run 70998 0.500000 m2enngR tau-e 0
run 66707 0.500000 m2enngR tau-e 0
...
run 70998 0.250000 m2enngR tau-e 0
...

run 70998 1.000000 m2enng0 tau-e 0
...

run 70998 1.000000 m2enngV tau-e 0
...

run 70998 0.500000 m2enngC tau-e 0
...
run 70998 0.250000 m2enngC tau-e 0
...
```

(a) Menu file menu-m2enn-tau-e.menu

```
## Generated at 16:00 on February 28 2020 by yannickulrich
# git version: redesign (b558978)
```

```
# specify the program to run relative to `pwd`
binary=mcmule

# specify the output folder
folder=babar-tau-e/

# Specify the variables nenter_ad, itmx_ad, nenter and itmx
# for each piece you want to run.
declare -A STAT=(
  ["m2enngR"]="5000\n50\n10000\n100"
  ["m2enng0"]="1000\n10\n1000\n50"
  ["m2enngV"]="1000\n10\n1000\n50"
  ["m2enngC"]="1000\n10\n1000\n50"
)
```

(b) Configuration file m2enng-tau-e.conf

Listing 8: The files required for the present calculations as generated in Listing 7. The file has been massively shortened for presentation. The full file is attached to this document

```
image yulrich/mcmule:latest path/to/user.f95
conf babar-tau-e/m2enng-tau-e.conf
```

```
run 70998 0.500000 m2enngR tau-e 0
...
```

Note that only one `image` command per menu file is allowed. After this, the menu file can be executed normally though the drive where Docker or `udocker` is installed needs to be shared between all nodes working on the job. It is recommended that all legacy results use be produced with `udocker` or Docker.

3 Analysis

After running the code, we need to combine the various `which_pieces` into physical results that we will want to use to create plots. For this purpose, we provide the python tool `pymule`, though of course other tools can be used as well. Here, we will only cover the aspects of `pymule` required for the present analysis as shown in Listing 9; a full documentation can be found in the `docstrings` used in `pymule` as well as Appendix D. First, we import `pymule`. Next, we need to point `pymule` to the output directory of `mcmule` with the `setup` command. In our example this is `babar-tau-e/out`.

As a next step, we import the LO and NLO `which_pieces` and combine them using two central `pymule` commands: `sigma` and `mergefks`. `sigma` takes the `which_piece` as an argument and imports matching results, already merging different random seeds. `mergefks` takes the results of (multiple) `sigma` invocations, adds results with matching ξ_c values and combines the result. In the present case, $\sigma_n^{(1)}$ is split into multiple contributions, namely `m2enngV` and `m2enngC`. This is indicated by the `anyxi` argument.

Users should keep in mind that MCMULE ships with a version of `global_def` where the couplings $G_F = \mathbf{GF}$ and $\alpha = \mathbf{alpha}$ are set to $G_F = \alpha = 1$. Hence, we use `pymule`'s function `scaleset` to multiply the result with the correct values of G_F (in MeV^{-1}) and α (in the OS scheme).

Next, we can use some of `pymule`'s tools (cf. Listing 9) to calculate the full NLO BRs from the corrections and the LO results

$$\mathcal{B}|_{\text{LO}} = 1.8339(1) \times 10^{-2}, \quad \mathcal{B}|_{\text{NLO}} = 1.6451(1) \times 10^{-2}, \quad (1)$$

which agree with [6, 24], but $\mathcal{B}|_{\text{NLO}}$ is in tension with the value $\mathcal{B}|_{\text{exp}} = 1.847(54) \times 10^{-2}$ reported by BABAR [20, 21]. As discussed in [6, 25] it is very likely that this tension would be removed if a full NLO result was used to take into account the effects of the stringent experimental cuts to extract the signal. This issue has been explained in detail in [2, 6, 25].

As a last step, we can use the `matplotlib`-backed `kplot` command to present the results for the distributions (logarithmic for $m_{e\gamma}$ and linear for E_e). The results are shown in Figure 10. The upper panel of Figure 10a shows the results for the invariant mass $m_{e\gamma}$ at LO (green) and NLO (blue) in the range $0 \leq m_{e\gamma} \leq 1 \text{ GeV}$. Note that this, for the purposes of the demonstration, does not correspond to the boundaries given in the run.

The distribution falls sharply for large $m_{e\gamma}$. Consequently, there are only few events generated in the tail and the statistical error becomes large. This can be seen clearly in the lower panel,

```

from pymule import *

# To normalise branching ratios, we need the tau lifetime
lifetime = 1/(1000*(6.582119e-25)/(2.903e-13))

# The folder where McMule has stored the statefiles
setup(folder='babar-tau-e/out.tar.bz2')

# Import LO data and re-scale to branching ratio
LO = scaleset(mergefks(sigma('m2enng0')), GF**2*lifetime*alpha)

# Import NLO corrections from the three pieces
NLO = scaleset(mergefks(
    sigma('m2enngR'),      # real corrections
    sigma('m2enngCT'),    # counter term
    anyxi=sigma('m2enngV') # virtual corrections
), GF**2*lifetime*alpha**2)

# The branching ratio at NLO = LO + correction
fullNLO = plusnumbers(LO['value'], NLO['value'])

# Print results
print("BR_0□=□", printnumber(LO['value']))
print("dBR_□□=□", printnumber(NLO['value']))

# Produce energy plot
fig1, (ax1, ax2) = kplot(
    {'lo': LO['Ee'], 'nlo': NLO['Ee']},
    labelx=r"$E_e\,/\/,\{\rm□MeV\}$",
    labelsigma=r"$\D\mathcal{B}/\D□E_e$"
)
ax2.set_ylim(-0.2,0.01)

# Produce visible mass plot
fig2, (ax1, ax2) = kplot(
    {'lo': LO['minv'], 'nlo': NLO['minv']},
    labelx=r"$m_{e\gamma}\,/\/,\{\rm□MeV\}$",
    labelsigma=r"$\D\mathcal{B}/\D□m_{e\gamma}$"
)
ax1.set_yscale('log')
ax1.set_xlim(1000,0) ; ax1.set_ylim(5e-9,1e-3)
ax2.set_ylim(-0.2,0.)

```

Listing 9: An example code to analyse the results for $\tau \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}e\gamma$ in pymule. Note that, in the Fortran code $G_F = \alpha = 1$. In pymule they are at their physical values [23].

Figure 10: Results of the toy run to compute $m_{e\gamma}$ (left) and E_e (right) for $\tau \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} e \gamma$. Upper panels show the LO (green) and NLO (blue) results, the lower panels show the NLO K factor.

where the NLO K factor is shown. It is defined as

$$K^{(1)} = 1 + \frac{d\sigma^{(1)}}{d\sigma^{(0)}}, \quad (2)$$

and the band represents the statistical error of the Monte Carlo integration. To obtain a reliable prediction for larger values of $m_{e\gamma}$, i.e. the tail of the distribution, we would have to perform tailored runs. To this end, we should introduce a cut $m_{\text{cut}} \ll m_\tau$ on $m_{e\gamma}$ to eliminate events with larger invariant mass. Due to the adaption in the numerical integration, we then obtain reliable and precise results for values of $m_{e\gamma} \lesssim m_{\text{cut}}$.

Figure 10b shows the electron energy distribution, again at LO (green) and NLO (blue). As for $m_{e\gamma}$ the corrections are negative and amount to roughly 10%. Since this plot is linear, they can be clearly seen by comparing LO and NLO. In the lower panel once more the K factor is depicted. Unsurprisingly, at the very end of the distribution, $E_e \sim 900$ MeV, the statistics is out of control.

4 General aspects of using MCMULE

In this section, we will collect a few general points of interest regarding MCMULE. In particular, we will discuss heuristics on how much statistics is necessary for different contributions in Section 4.1. This is followed by a more in-depth discussion of the analysis strategy in Section 4.2.

4.1 Statistics

MCMULE is a Monte Carlo program. This means it samples the integrand at N (pseudo-)random points to get an estimate for the integral. However, because it uses the adaptive Monte Carlo integration routine `vegas` [16], we split $N = i \times n$ into i iterations (`itmx`), each with n points (`nenter`). After each iteration, `vegas` changes the way it will sample the next iteration based on the results of the previous one. Hence, the performance of the integration is a subtle interplay between i and n – it is not sufficient any more to consider their product N .

Further, we always perform the integration in two steps: a pre-conditioning with $i_{\text{ad}} \times n_{\text{ad}}$ (`nenter_ad` and `itmx_ad`, respectively), that is used to optimise the integration strategy and after which the result is discarded, and a main integration that benefits from the integrator’s understanding of the integrand.

Of course there are no one-size-fits-all rules of how to choose the i and n for pre-conditioning and main run. However, the following heuristics have proven helpful:

- n is always much larger than i . For very simple integrands, $n = \mathcal{O}(10 \cdot 10^3)$ and $i = \mathcal{O}(10)$.
- Increasing n reduces errors that can be thought of as systematic because it allows the integrator to ‘discover’ new features of the integrand. Increasing i on the other hand will rarely have that effect and only improves the statistical error. This is especially true for distributions.
- There is no real limit on n , except that it has to fit into the datatype used – integrations with $n = \mathcal{O}(2^{31} - 1)$ are not too uncommon – while i is rarely (much) larger than 100.
- For very stringent cuts it can happen that that typical values of n_{ad} are too small for any point to pass the cuts. In this case `vegas` will return `NaN`, indicating that no events were found. Barring mistakes in the definition of the cuts, a pre-pre-conditioning with extremely large n but $i = 1 - 2$ can be helpful.
- n also needs to be large enough for `vegas` to reliably find all features of the integrand. It is rarely obvious that it did, though sometimes it becomes clear when increasing n or looking at intermediary results as a function of the already-completed iterations.
- The main run should always have larger i and n than the pre-conditioning. Judging how much more is a delicate game though $i/i_{\text{ad}} = \mathcal{O}(5)$ and $n/n_{\text{ad}} = \mathcal{O}(10 - 50)$ have been proven helpful.
- If, once the integration is completed, the result is unsatisfactory, take into account the following strategies
 - A large $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}$ indicates a too small n . Try to increase n_{ad} and, to a perhaps lesser extent, n .
 - Increase i . Often it is a good idea to consciously set i to a value so large that the integrator will never reach it and to keep looking at ‘intermediary’ results.
 - If the error is small enough for the application but the result seems incorrect (for example because the ξ_c dependence does not vanish), massively increase n .
- Real corrections need much more statistics in both i and n ($\mathcal{O}(10)$ times more for n , $\mathcal{O}(2)$ for i) than the corresponding LO calculations because of the higher-dimensional phase-space.
- Virtual corrections have the same number of dimensions as the LO calculation and can go by with only a modest increase to account for the added functional complexity.
- `vegas` tends to underestimate the numerical error.

These guidelines are often helpful but should not be considered infallible as they are just that – guidelines.

MCMULE is not parallelised; however, because Monte Carlo integrations require a random seed anyway, it is possible to calculate multiple estimates of the same integral using different random seeds z_1 and combining the results obtained this way. This also allows to for a better, more reliable understanding of the error estimate.

4.2 Analysis

Once the Monte Carlo has run, an offline analysis of the results is required. This entails loading, averaging, and combining the data. This is automatised in `pymule` but the basic steps are

0. Load the data into a suitable analysis framework such as `python`.
1. Combine the different random seeds into one result per contribution and ξ_c . The $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}$ of this merging must be small. Otherwise, try to increase the statistics or choose of different phase-space parametrisation.
2. Add all contributions that combine into one of the physical contributions (25b). This includes any partitioning done in Section 5.1.
3. (optional) At $N^\ell\text{LO}$, perform a fit⁸

$$\sigma_{n+j}^{(\ell)} = c_0^{(j)} + c_1^{(j)} \log \xi_c + c_2^{(j)} \log^2 \xi_c + \dots + c_\ell^{(j)} \log^\ell = \sum_{i=0}^{\ell} c_i^{(j)} \log^i \xi_c. \quad (3)$$

This has the advantage that it very clearly quantifies any residual ξ_c dependence. We will come back to this issue in Section 6.2.

4. Combine all physical contributions of (25a) into $\sigma^{(\ell)}(\xi_c)$ which has to be ξ_c independent.
5. Perform detailed checks on ξ_c independence. This is especially important on the first time a particular configuration is run. Beyond NLO, it is also extremely helpful to check whether the sum of the fits (3) is compatible with a constant, i.e. whether for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell$

$$\left| \frac{\sum_{j=0}^{\ell} c_i^{(j)}}{\sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \delta c_i^{(j)}} \right| < 1, \quad (4)$$

where $\delta c_i^{(j)}$ is the error estimate on the coefficient $c_i^{(j)}$.⁹ `pymule`'s `mergefkswithplot` can be helpful here.

If (4) is not satisfied or only very poorly, try to run the Monte Carlo again with an increased n .

⁸Note that it is important to perform the fit after combining the phase-space partitionings (cf. Section 5.1) but before adding (25a) as this model is only valid for the terms of (25b)

⁹Note that the error estimate on the sum of the total coefficients in (4) is rather poor and does not include correlations between different c_i .

6. Merge the different estimates of (25a) from the different ξ_c into one final number $\sigma^{(\ell)}$. The $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}$ of this merging must be small.
7. Repeat the above for any distributions produced, though often bin-wise fitting as in Point 3 is rarely necessary or helpful.

If a total cross section is ξ_c independent but the distributions (or a cross section obtained after applying cuts) are not, this is a hint that the distribution (or the applied cuts) is not IR safe.

These steps have been almost completely automatised in `pymule` and `Mathematica`. Though all steps of this pipeline could be easily implemented in any other language by following the specification of the file format below (Section 5.4).

5 Technical aspects of MCMULE

In this section, we will review the very technical details of the implementation. This is meant for those readers, who wish to truly understand the nuts and bolts holding the code together. We begin by discussing the phase-space generation and potential pitfalls in Section 5.1. Next, in Section 5.2, we discuss how the FKS scheme [2, 5, 26–28] (cf. Appendix A for a review) is implemented in Fortran code. This is followed by a brief review of the random number generator used in MCMULE in Section 5.3. Finally, we give an account of how the statefiles work and how they are used to store distributions in Section 5.4.

5.1 Phase-space generation

We use the `vegas` algorithm for numerical integration [16]. As `vegas` only works on the hypercube, we need a routine that maps $[0, 1]^{3n-4}$ to the momenta of an n -particle final state, including the corresponding Jacobian. The simplest way to do this uses iterative two-particle phase-spaces and boosting the generated momenta all back into the frame under consideration. An example of how this is done is shown in Listing 11.

As soon as we start using FKS, we cannot use this simplistic approach any longer. The c -distributions of FKS require the photon energies ξ_i to be variables of the integration. We can fix this by first generating the photon explicitly as

$$k_1 = p_{n+1} = \frac{\sqrt{s}}{2} \xi_1 (1, \sqrt{1 - y_1^2} \vec{e}_\perp, y_1), \quad (5)$$

where \vec{e}_\perp is a $(d - 2)$ dimensional unit vector and the ranges of y_1 (the cosine of the angle) and ξ_1 (the scaled energy) are $-1 \leq y_1 \leq 1$ and $0 \leq \xi_1 \leq \xi_{\max}$, respectively. The upper bound ξ_{\max} depends on the masses of the outgoing particles. Following [27] we find

$$\xi_{\max} = 1 - \frac{\left(\sum_i m_i\right)^2}{s}. \quad (6)$$

Finally, the remaining particles are generated iteratively again. This can always be done and is guaranteed to work.

For processes with one or more PCSs this approach is suboptimal. The numerical integration can be improved by orders of magnitude by aligning the pseudo-singular contribution to one

of the variables of the integration, as this allows `vegas` to optimise the integration procedure accordingly. As an example, consider once again $\mu \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}e\gamma$. The PCS comes from

$$\mathcal{M}_{n+1}^{(\ell)} \propto \frac{1}{q \cdot k} = \frac{1}{\xi^2} \frac{1}{1 - y\beta}, \quad (7)$$

where y is the angle between photon (k) and electron (q). For large velocities β (or equivalently small masses), this becomes almost singular as $y \rightarrow 1$. If now y is a variable of the integration this can be mediated. An example implementation is shown in Listing 12.

The approach outlined above is very easy to do in the case of the muon decay as the neutrinos can absorb any timelike four-momentum. This is because the δ function of the phase-space was solved through the neutrino's `pair_dec`. However, for scattering processes where all final state leptons could be measured, this fails. Writing a routine for μ - e -scattering

$$e(p_1) + \mu(p_2) \rightarrow e(p_3) + \mu(p_4) + \gamma(p_5), \quad (8)$$

that optimises on the incoming electron is rather trivial because its direction stays fixed s.t. the photon just needs to be generated according to (5). The outgoing electron p_3 is more complicated. Writing the p_4 -phase-space four- instead of three-dimensional

$$d\Phi_5 = \delta^{(4)}(p_1 + p_2 - p_3 - p_4 - p_5) \delta(p_4^2 - M^2) \Theta(E_4) \frac{d^4\vec{p}_4}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{d^3\vec{p}_3}{(2\pi)^3 2E_3} \frac{d^3\vec{p}_5}{(2\pi)^3 2E_5}, \quad (9)$$

we can solve the four-dimensional δ function for p_4 and proceed for the generation p_3 and p_5 almost as for the muon decay above. Doing this we obtain for the final δ function

$$\delta(p_4^2 - M^2) = \delta\left(m^2 - M^2 + s(1 - \xi) + E_3\sqrt{s}\left[\xi - 2 - y\xi\beta_3(E_3)\right]\right). \quad (10)$$

When solving this for E_3 , we need to take care to avoid extraneous solutions of this radical equation [29]. We have now obtained our phase-space parametrisation, albeit with one caveat: for anti-collinear photons, i.e. $-1 < y < 0$ with energies

$$\xi_1 = 1 - \frac{m}{\sqrt{s}} + \frac{M^2}{\sqrt{s}(m - \sqrt{s})} < \xi < \xi_{\max} = 1 - \frac{(m + M)^2}{s} \quad (11)$$

there are still two solutions. One of these corresponds to very low-energy electron that are almost produced at rest. This is rather fortunate as most experiments will have an electron detection threshold higher than this. Otherwise, phase-spaces optimised this way also define a `which_piece` for this corner region.

There is one last subtlety when it comes to these type of phase-space optimisations. Optimising the phase-space for emission from one leg often has adverse effects on terms with dominant emission from another leg. In other words, the numerical integration works best if there is only one PCS on which the phase-space is tuned. As most processes have more than one PCS we need to resort to something that was already discussed in the original FKS paper [26]. Scattering processes that involve multiple massless particles have overlapping singular regions. The FKS scheme now mandates that the phase-space is partitioned in such a way as to isolate at most one singularity per region with each region having its own phase-space parametrisation. Similarly

we have to split the phase-space to contain at most one PCS as well as the soft singularity. In MCMULE μ - e scattering for instance is split as follows¹⁰

$$1 = \theta(s_{15} > s_{35}) + \theta(s_{15} < s_{35}), \quad (12)$$

with $s_{ij} = 2p_i \cdot p_j$ as usual. The integrand of the first θ function has a final-state PCS and hence we use the parametrisation obtained by solving (10). The second θ function, on the other hand, has an initial-state PCS which can be treated by just directly parametrising the photon in the centre-of-mass frame as per (5). This automatically makes $s_{15} \propto (1 - \beta_{\text{in}} y_1)$ a variable of the integration.

For the double-real corrections of μ - e scattering, we proceed along the same lines except now the argument of the δ function is more complicated.

5.2 Implementation of FKS schemes

Now that we have a phase-space routine that has ξ_i as variables of the integration, we can start implementing the relevant c -distributions (21)

$$\begin{aligned} d\sigma_h^{(1)}(\xi_c) &= d\Upsilon_1 d\Phi_{n,1} \left(\frac{1}{\xi_1} \right)_c d\xi_1 \left(\xi_1^2 \mathcal{M}_{n+1}^{(0)} \right) \\ &= d\xi_1 \frac{1}{\xi_1} \left(d\Upsilon_1 d\Phi_{n,1} \left(\xi_1^2 \mathcal{M}_{n+1}^{(0)} \right) - d\Upsilon_1 d\Phi_{n,1} \left(\mathcal{E} \mathcal{M}_n^{(0)} \right) \theta(\xi_c - \xi_1) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

We refer to the first term as the event and the second as the counter-event.

Note that, due to the presence of $\delta(\xi_1)$ in the counter-event (that is implemented through the eikonal factor \mathcal{E}) the momenta generated by the phase-space $d\Upsilon_1 d\Phi_{n,1}$ are different. Thus, it is possible that the momenta of the event pass the cuts or on-shell conditions, while those of the counter event fail, or vice versa. This subtlety is extremely important to properly implement the FKS scheme and many problems fundamentally trace back to this.

Finally, we should note that, in order to increase numerical stability, we introduce cuts on ξ and sometimes also on a parameter that encodes the PCS such as $y = y_2$ in (5) and Listing 12. Events that have values of ξ smaller than this soft cut are discarded immediately and no subtraction is considered. The dependence on this slicing parameter is not expected to drop out completely and hence, the soft cut has to be chosen small enough to not influence the result.

An example implementation can be found in Listing 13.

5.3 Random number generation

A Monte Carlo integrator relies on a (pseudo) *random number generator* (RNG or PRNG) to work. The pseudo-random numbers need to be of high enough quality, i.e. have no discernible pattern and a long period, to consider each point of the integration independent but the RNG needs to be simple enough to be called many billion times without being a significant source of runtime. RNGs used in Monte Carlo applications are generally poor in quality and often predictable s.t. they could not be used for cryptographic applications.

¹⁰When implementing this, care must be taken to ensure that the split is also well defined if the photon is soft, i.e. if $\xi = 0$.

```

! use a random number to decide how much energy should
! go into the first particle
minv3 = ra(1)*energy

! use two random numbers to generate the momenta of
! particles 1 and the remainder in the CMS frame
call pair_dec(ra(2:3),energy,q2,m2,qq3,minv3)

! adjust the Jacobian
weight = minv3*energy/pi
weight = weight*0.125*sq_lambda(energy**2,m2,minv3)/energy**2/pi

! use a random number to decide how much energy should
! go into the second particle
minv4 = ra(4)*energy
! use two random numbers to generate the momenta of
! particles 2 and the remainder in their rest frame
call pair_dec(ra(5:6),minv3,q3,m3,qq4,minv4)

! adjust the Jacobian
weight = weight*minv4*energy/pi
weight = weight*0.125*sq_lambda(minv3**2,m3,minv4)/minv3**2/pi

! repeat this process until all particles are generated

! boost all generated particles back into the CMS frame

q4 = boost_back(qq4, q4)
q5 = boost_back(qq4, q5)

q3 = boost_back(qq3, q3)
q4 = boost_back(qq3, q4)
q5 = boost_back(qq3, q5)

```

Listing 11: Example implementation of iterative phase-space. Not shown are the checks to make sure that all particles have at least enough energy for their mass, i.e. that $E_i \geq m_i$.

```

xi5 = ra(1)
y2 = 2*ra(2) - 1.

! generate electron q2 and photon q5 s.t. that the
! photon goes into z diractions

eme = energy*ra(3)
pme = sqrt(eme**2-m2**2)
q2 = (/ 0., pme*sqrt(1. - y2**2), pme*y2, eme /)
q5 = (/ 0., 0., 1., 1. /)
q5 = 0.5*energy*xi5*q5

! generate euler angles and rotate all momenta

euler_mat = get_euler_mat(ra(4:6))

q2 = matmul(euler_mat,q2)
q5 = matmul(euler_mat,q5)

qq34 = q1-q2-q5
minv34 = sqrt(sq(qq34))

! The event weight, note that a factor xi5**2 has been ommited
weight = energy**3*pme/(4.*(2.*pi)**4)

! generate remaining neutrino momenta

call pair_dec(ra(7:8),minv34,q3,m3,q4,m4,enough_energy)
weight = weight*0.125*sq_lambda(minv34**2,m3,m4)/minv34**2/pi

q3 = boost_back(qq34,q3)
q4 = boost_back(qq34,q4)

```

Listing 12: Example implementation of a so-called FKS phase-space where the fifth particle is an FKS photon that may becomes soft. Not shown are checks whether $E_i \geq m_i$.

```

FUNCTION SIGMA_1(x, wgt, ndim)

! The first random number x(1) is xi.
arr = x

! Generate momenta for the event using the function pointer ps
call gen_mom_fks(ps, x, masses(1:nparticle), vecs, weight)

! Whether unphysical or not, take the value of xi
xifix = xiout

! Check if the event is physical ...
if(weight > zero ) then
! and whether it passes the cuts
var = quant(vecs(:,1), vecs(:,2), vecs(:,3), vecs(:,4), ...)
cuts = any(pass_cut)
if(cuts) then
! Calculate the xi**2 * M_{n+1}^0 using the pointer matel
mat = matel(vecs(:,1), vecs(:,2), vecs(:,3), vecs(:,4), ...)
mat = xifix*weight*mat
sigma_1 = mat
end if
end if

! Check whether soft subtraction is required
if(xifix < xicut1) then
! Implement the delta function and regenerate events
arr(1) = 0._prec
call gen_mom_fks(ps, arr, masses(1:nparticle), vecs, weight)
! Check whether to include the counter event
if(weight > zero) then
var = quant(vecs(:,1), vecs(:,2), vecs(:,3), vecs(:,4), ...)
cuts = any(pass_cut)
if(cuts) then
mat = matel_s(vecs(:,1), vecs(:,2), vecs(:,3), vecs(:,4),
↪ ...)
mat = weight*mat/xifix
sigma_1 = sigma_1 - mat
endif
endif
endif
END FUNCTION SIGMA_1

```

Listing 13: An example implementation of the FKS scheme in Fortran. Not shown are various checks performed, the binning as well as initialisation blocks.

A commonly used trade-off between unpredictability and simplicity, both in speed and implementation, is the Park-Miller RNG, also known as `minstd` [30]. As a linear congruential generator, its $(k + 1)$ th output x_{k+1} can be found as

$$z_{k+1} = a \cdot z_k \bmod m = a^{k+1} z_1 \bmod m \quad \text{and} \quad x_k = z_k/m \in (0, 1), \quad (14)$$

where m is a large, preferably prime, number and $2 < a < m - 1$ an integer. The initial value z_1 is called the random seed and is chosen integer between 1 and $m - 1$. It can easily be seen that any such RNG has a fixed period¹¹ $p < m$ s.t. $z_{k+p} = z_k$ because any z_{k+1} only depends on z_k and there are finitely many possible z_k . We call the RNG attached to (m, a) to be of full period if $p = m - 1$, i.e. all integers between 1 and $m - 1$ appear in the sequence z_k .

Assuming $z_1 = 1$ then the existence of p s.t. $z_{p+1} = 1$ is guaranteed by Fermat's Theorem¹². This means that the RNG is of full period iff a is a primitive root modulo m , i.e.

$$\forall g \text{ co-prime to } m \quad \exists k \in \mathbb{Z} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad a^k \equiv g \pmod{m}. \quad (15)$$

Park and Miller suggest to use the Mersenne prime $m = 2^{31} - 1$, noting that there are 534,600,000 primitive roots of which 7 is the smallest. Because $7^b \bmod m$ is also a primitive root as long as b is co-prime to $(m - 1)$, [30] settled on $b = 5$, i.e. $a = 16807$ as a good choice for the multiplier that, per construction, has full period and passes certain tests of randomness.

The points generated by any such RNG will fall into $\sqrt[n]{n! \cdot m}$ hyperplanes if scattered in an n dimensional space [31]. However, for bad choices of the multiplier a the number of planes can be a lot smaller¹³.

Presently, the period length of $p = m - 1 = 2^{31} - 2$ is believed to be sufficient though detailed studies quantifying this would be welcome.

5.4 Differential distributions and intermediary state files

Distributions are always calculated as histograms by binning each event according to its value for the observable S . This is done by having an $(n_b \times n_q)$ -dimensional array¹⁴ `quant` where n_q is the number of histograms to be calculated (`nr_q`) and n_b is the number of bins used (`nr_bins`). The weight of each event $d\Phi \times \mathcal{M} \times w$ is added to the correct entry in `bit_it` where $w = \text{wgt}$ is the event weight assigned by `vegas`.

After each iteration of `vegas` we add `quant` (`quant2`) to an accumulator of the same dimensions called `quantsum` (`quantsumsq`). After i iterations, we can calculate the value and error as

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dS} \approx \frac{\text{quantsum}}{\Delta \times i} \quad \text{and} \quad \delta\left(\frac{d\sigma}{dS}\right) \approx \frac{1}{\Delta} \sqrt{\frac{\text{quantsumsq} - \text{quantsum}^2/i}{i(i-1)}}, \quad (16)$$

where Δ is the bin-size.

¹¹Note that, because of the simple recursion the RNG will not repeat any number until the full period is complete

¹²If p is prime, for any integer a , $a^p - a$ is a multiple of p .

¹³An infamous example is `randu` that used $a = 2^{16} + 3$ and $m = 2^{31}$ that in three dimension produces only 15 planes instead of the maximum 2344.

¹⁴To be precise, the actual dimensions are $(n_b + 2) \times n_q$ to accommodate under- and overflow bins

Related to this discussion is the concept of intermediary state files. Their purpose is to record the complete state of the integrator after every iteration in order to recover should the program crash – or more likely be interrupted by a batch system. MCMULE uses a custom file format `.vegas` for this purpose which uses Fortran’s record-based (instead of stream- or byte-based) format. This means that each entry starts with 32bit unsigned integer, i.e. 4 byte, indicating the record’s size and ends with the same 32bit integer. As this is automatically done for each record, it minimises the amount of metadata that have to be written.

The current version (`v3`) must begin with the magic header and version self-identification shown in Figure 14. The latter includes file version information and the first five characters the source tree’s SHA1 hash, obtained using `make hash`.

The header is followed by records describing the state of the integrator as shown in Figure 15. Additionally to information required to continue integration such as the current value and grid information, this file also has 300 bytes for a message. This is usually set by the routine to store information on the fate of the integration such as whether it was so-far uninterrupted or whether there is reason to believe it to be inconsistent.

The latter point is particularly important. While MCMULE cannot read intermediary files from a different version of the file format, it will continue any integration for which it can read the state file. This also includes cases where the source tree has been changed. In this case MCMULE prints a warning but continues the integration deriving potentially inconsistent results.

5.5 Basics of containerisation

MCMULE is Docker-compatible. Production runs should be performed with Docker [3], or its user-space complement *udocker* [4], to facilitate reproducibility and data retention. On Linux, Docker uses `chroot` to simulate an operating system with MCMULE installed. In our case, the underlying system is Alpine Linux, a Linux distribution that is approximately 5MB in size.

5.5.1 Terminology

To understand Docker, we need to introduce some terms

- An image is a representation of the system’s ‘hard disk’. One host system can have multiple images. In (u)Docker, the images can be listed with `docker image ls` (`udocker images`).
- Images can be have names, called tags, otherwise Docker assigns a name as the SHA256 hash.
- Because keeping multiple full file systems is rather wasteful, images are split into layers that can be shared among images. In *uDocker*, these are tar files containing the changes made to the file system.
- To execute an image, a container needs to be generated. Essentially, this involves uncompressing all layers into a directory and `chrooting` into said directory.

It is important to note, that containers are ephemeral, i.e. changes made to the container are not stored unless explicitly requested. This is usually not required anyway.

For external interfacing, folders of the host system are mounted into the container.

offset	00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	0A	0B	0C	0D	0E	0F
hex	09	00	00	00	20	4D	63	4D	75	6C	65	20	20	09	00	00
ASCII	\t				' '	M	c	M	u	l	e	' '	' '	\t		
offset	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	1A	1B	1C	1D	1E	1F
hex	00	0A	00	00	00	76	xx	xx	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	0A
ASCII		\n				v	v_1	v_2	' '	' '	' '	' '	' '	' '	' '	\n
offset	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	2A	2B	2C	2D	2E	2F
hex	00	00	00	05	00	00	00	xx	xx	xx	xx	xx	05	00	00	00
ASCII								s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	s_5				

Figure 14: The magic header and version information used by `v3`. v_1 indicates the current version number and v_2 whether long integers are used (L) or not (N). s_1 - s_5 indicate the first five characters of the SHA1 hash produced by the source code at compile time (`make hash`).

Off	Len	Type	Var.	Comment
0030	000C	integer	it	the current iteration
003C	000C	integer	ndo	subdiv. on an axis
0048	0010	real	si	$\sigma/(\delta\sigma)^2$
0058	0010	real	swgt	$1/(\delta\sigma)^2$
0068	0010	real	schi	$(1 - \text{it})\chi + \sigma^2/(\delta\sigma)^2$
0078	1A98	real(50,17)	xi	the integration grid
1B10	000C	integer	randy	the current random number seed
1B1C	0014	integer integer integer	n_q n_b n_s	number of histograms number of bins len. histogram name
1B30	$10n_q + 8$	real(n_q) real(n_q)	minv maxv	lower bounds upper bounds
	$n_s n_q + 8$	character(n_s, n_q)	names	names of S
	$10n_q(n_b + 2) + 8$	real(n_q, n_b+2) real(n_q, n_b+2)	quantsum quantsumsq	accu. histograms accu. histograms squared
-0144	0010	real	time	current runtime in seconds
-0134	0134	character(300)	msg	any message
-0000			EOF	

Figure 15: The body of a `.vegas` file storing all important information. Each horizontal line indicates as dressed record. In the offset and length columns, all integers are in hexadecimal notation. Negative numbers count from the end of file (EOF).

5.5.2 Building images

Docker images are built using Dockerfiles, a set of instruction on how to create the image from external information and a base image. To speed up building of the image, MCMULE uses a custom base image called `mcmule-pre` that is constructed as follows

```
FROM alpine:3.11

LABEL maintainer="yannick.ulrich@psi.ch"
LABEL version="1.0"
LABEL description="The base image for the full McMule suite"

# Install a bunch of things
RUN apk add py3-numpy py3-scipy ipython py3-pip git tar gfortran
    ↪ gcc make curl musl-dev
RUN echo "http://dl-8.alpinelinux.org/alpine/edge/community" >> /
    ↪ etc/apk/repositories && \
    apk add py3-matplotlib && \
    sed -i '$d' /etc/apk/repositories
```

On top of this, MCMULE is build

```
FROM yulrich/mcmule-pre:1.0.0

LABEL maintainer="yannick.ulrich@psi.ch"
LABEL version="1.0"
LABEL description="The full McMule suite"
RUN pip3 install git+gitlab.com/mule-tools/pymule.git
COPY . /monte-carlo
WORKDIR /monte-carlo
RUN ./configure
RUN make
```

To build this image, run

```
monte-carlo$ docker build -t $mytagname . # Using Docker
monte-carlo$ udocker build -t=$mytagname . # Using udocker
```

The CI system uses `udocker` to perform builds after each push. Note that using `udocker` for building requires a patched version of the code that is available from the MMCT.

5.5.3 Creating containers and running

In Docker, containers are usually created and run in one command

```
$ docker run --rm $imagename $cmd
```

The flag `-rm` makes sure the container is deleted after it is completed. If the command is a shell (usually `ash`), the flag `-i` also needs to be provided.

For `udocker`, creation and running can be done in two steps

```

FUNCTION EE2EE(p1, p2, p3, p4)
  !! e-(p1) e-(p2) -> e-(p3) e-(p4)
  !! for massive (and massless) electrons
  implicit none
  real(kind=prec), intent(in) :: p1(4), p2(4), p3(p4), p4(4), ee2ee
  real(kind=prec) :: den1, den2, t, scms, m2
  t = sq(p1-p3) ; scms = sq(p1+p2) ; m2 = sq(p1)
  den1 = sq(p1-p3) ; den2 = sq(p1-p4)

  ee2ee=(8**m2**2 - 8*m2*scms + 2*s**2 + 2*scms*t + t**2)/den1**2
  ee2ee=ee2ee+2*(12*m2**2 - 8*m2*scms + scms**2) / den1 / den2
  ee2ee=ee2ee+(24*m2**2 + scms**2 + t**2 - 8*m2*(s + t))/den2**2

  ee2ee = ee2ee * 128*pi**2*alpha**2
END FUNCTION

```

Listing 16: An example implementation of $\mathcal{M}_n^{(0)}$ for Møller scattering. Note that the electron mass and the centre-of-mass energy are calculated locally. A global factor of $8e^4 = 128\pi^2\alpha^2$ is included at the end.

```

$ udocker create $imagename
# this prints the container id
$ udocker run $containerid $cmd
# work in container
$ udocker rm $containerid

```

or in one step

```
$ udocker run --rm $imagename $cmd
```

Running containers can be listed with `udocker ps` and `docker ps`. For further details, the reader is pointed to the manuals of Docker and *udocker*.

6 Implementing new processes in MCMULE

In this section we will discuss how new processes can be added to MCMULE. Not all of the points below might be applicable to any particular process. Further, all points are merely guidelines that could be deviated from if necessary as long as proper precautions are taken.

As an example, we will discuss how Møller scattering $e^-e^- \rightarrow e^-e^-$ could be implemented.

1. A new process group may need to be created if the process does not fit any of the presently implemented groups. This requires a new folder with a makefile as well as modifications to the main makefile as discussed in Section 6.1.

In our case, $ee \rightarrow ee$ does not fit any of the groups, so we create a new group that we shall call `ee`.

2. Calculate the tree-level matrix elements needed at LO and NLO: $\mathcal{M}_n^{(0)}$ and $\mathcal{M}_{n+1}^{(0)}$. This is relatively straightforward and – crucially – unambiguous as both are finite in $d = 4$. We will come back to an example calculation in Section 6.3.
3. A generic matrix element file is needed to store ‘simple’ matrix elements as well as importing more complicated matrix elements. Usually, this file should not contain matrix elements that are longer than a few dozen or so lines. In most cases, this applies to $\mathcal{M}_n^{(0)}$.

After each matrix element, the PID needs to be denoted in a comment. Further, all required masses as well as the centre-of-mass energy, called `scms` to avoid collisions with the function $\mathbf{s}(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j) = 2\mathbf{p}_i \cdot \mathbf{p}_j$, need to be calculated in the matrix element to be as localised as possible.

In the case of Møller scattering, a file `ee/ee_mat_e1.f95` will contain $\mathcal{M}_n^{(0)}$. For example, $\mathcal{M}_n^{(0)}$ is implemented there as shown in Listing 16.

4. Further, we need an interface file that also contains the soft limits. In our case this is called `ee/ee.f95`.
5. Because $\mathcal{M}_{n+1}^{(0)}$ is border-line large, we will assume that it will be stored in an extra file, `ee/ee2eeg.f95`. The required functions are to be imported in `ee/ee_mat_e1.f95`.
6. Calculate the one-loop virtual matrix element $\mathcal{M}_n^{(1)}$, renormalised in the OS scheme. Of course, this could be done in any regularisation scheme. However, results in MCMULE shall be in the FDH (or equivalently the FDF) scheme. Divergent matrix elements in MCMULE are implemented as c_{-1} , c_0 , and c_1

$$\mathcal{M}_n^{(1)} = \frac{(4\pi)^\epsilon}{\Gamma(1-\epsilon)} \left(\frac{c_{-1}}{\epsilon} + c_0 + c_1\epsilon + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2) \right). \quad (17)$$

For c_{-1} and c_0 this is equivalent to the conventions employed by Package-X [32] up to a factor $1/16\pi^2$. While not strictly necessary, it is generally advisable to also include c_{-1} in the Fortran code.

For NLO calculations, c_1 does not enter. However, we wish to include Møller scattering up to NNLO and hence will need it sooner rather than later anyway.

In our case, we will create a file `ee/ee_ee2eel.f95`, which defines a function

```

FUNCTION EE2EE1(p1, p2, p3, p4, sing, lin)
  !! e-(p1) e-(p2) -> e-(p3) e-(p4)
  !! for massive electrons
  implicit none
  real(kind=prec), intent(in) :: p1(4), p2(4), p3(4), p4(4)
  real(kind=prec) :: ee2eel
  real(kind=prec), intent(out), optional :: sing, lin
  ...
END FUNCTION

```

The function shall return c_0 in `ee2eel` and, if present c_{-1} and c_1 in `sing` and `lin`.

7. At this stage, a new subroutine in the program `test` with reference values for all three matrix elements should be written to test the Fortran implementation. This is done by generating a few points using an appropriate phase-space routine and comparing to as many digits as possible using the routine `check`.

In our case, we would construct a subroutine `TESTEEMATEL` as shown in Listing 17

8. Define a default observable in `user` for this process. This observable must be defined for any `which_piece` that might have been defined and test all relevant features of the implementation such as polarisation if applicable.
9. Add the matrix elements to the integrands defined in `integrand.f95` as discussed above. These integrands should be added to `mcmule.f95` and a second test routine should be written that runs short integrations against a reference value. Because `test_INT` uses a fixed random seed, this is expected to be possible very precisely. Unfortunately, COLLIER [10] might produce slightly different results on different machines. Hence, integrands involving complicated loop functions are only required to agree up to $\mathcal{O}(10^{-8})$.
10. After some short test runs, it should be clear whether new phase-space routines are required. Add those, if need be, to `phase_space` as described in Section 5.1.
11. Per default the stringent soft cut, that may be required to stabilise the numerical integration (cf. Section 5.2), is set to zero. Study what the smallest value is that still permits integration.
12. Perform very precise ξ_c independence studies. Tips on how to do this can be found in Section 6.2.

At this stage, the NLO calculation is complete and may, after proper integration into `MCMULE` and adherence to coding style has been confirmed, be added to the list of `MCMULE` processes in a new release. Should NNLO precision be required, the following steps should be taken

13. Calculate the real-virtual and double-real matrix elements $\mathcal{M}_{n+1}^{(1)}$ and $\mathcal{M}_{n+2}^{(0)}$ and add them to the test routines as well as integrands.
14. Prepare the n -particle contribution $\sigma_n^{(2)}$. In a pinch, massified results can be used also for $\hat{\mathcal{E}}(\xi_c)\mathcal{M}_n^{(1)}$ though of course one should default to the fully massive results.
15. Study whether the pre-defined phase-space routines are sufficient. Even if it was possible to use an old phase-space at NLO, this might no longer work at NNLO due to the added complexity. Adapt and partition further if necessary, adding more test integrations in the process.
16. Perform yet more detailed ξ_c and soft cut analyses.

In the following we comment on a few aspects of this procedure such as the ξ_c study (Section 6.2), the calculation of matrix elements (Section 6.3), and a brief style guide for `MCMULE` code (Section 6.4).

```

SUBROUTINE TESTEEMATEL
implicit none
real (kind=prec) :: x(2),y(5)
real (kind=prec) :: single, finite, lin
real (kind=prec) :: weight
integer ido

call blockstart("ee_matrix_elements")
scms = 40000.
musq = me
x = (/0.75,0.5/)
call ps_x2(x,scms,p1,me,p2,me,p3,me,p4,me,weight)
call check("ee2ee",ee2ee(p1,p2,p3,p4), 2.273983244890001e4,
  ↪ threshold=2e-8)
call check("ee2eel",ee2eel(p1,p2,p3,p4), 6.964297070440638e7,
  ↪ threshold=2e-8)

scms = 40000.
y = (/0.3,0.6,0.8,0.4,0.9/)
call ps_x3_fks(y,scms,p1,me,p2,me,p3,me,p4,me,p5,weight)
call check("ee2eeg",ee2eeg(p1,p2,p3,p4,p5),7.864297444955537e2,
  ↪ threshold=2e-8)

call blockend(3)
END SUBROUTINE

SUBROUTINE TESTMEEVEGAS
xinormcut1 = 0.2
xinormcut2 = 0.3

call blockstart("Moller_VEGAS_test")

call test_INT('ee2ee0', sigma_0, 2,10,10, ??)
call test_INT('ee2eeF', sigma_0, 2,10,10, ??)
call test_INT('ee2eeR', sigma_1, 5,10,10, ??)
call blockend(3)
END SUBROUTINE

```

Listing 17: Test routine for $ee \rightarrow ee$ matrix elements and integrands. The reference values for the integration are yet to be determined.

```

group=ee
AUXFILES=ee_ee2eel.f95 ee_ee2eeg.f95

MAIN=$(group)_mat_el.f95 $(group).f95

include ../makefile.conf

all: $(group).a $(group).mod .obj/tree.sha

$(OBJ): ../.obj/functions.mod

.obj/$(group)_mat_el.o .obj/$(group)_mat_el.mod: \
    $(group)_mat_el.f95 $(MOD)
.obj/$(group).o .obj/$(group).mod: \
    $(group).f95 .obj/$(group)_mat_el.mod $(MOD)

$(group).mod: .obj/$(group).mod
    cp $< $@

$(group).a:$(OBJ)
    @echo AR $@
    @$ (AR) $@ $^

clean:
    rm -f .obj/*.o .obj/*.mod .obj/*.gcda .obj/*.gcno *.mod *.a

```

Listing 18: The bare makefile for the new process group `ee`. Large matrix elements that are stored in extra files such as `ee/ee2eeg.f95` or `ee/ee2eel.f95` need to be added to the list of `AUXFILES`

6.1 Creating a new process group

Adding Møller scattering to MCMULE, the example discussed above, requires the addition of a new process group `ee`. For this we create a new folder in MCMULE called `ee` containing a makefile (Listing 18), a `mat_el` file (`ee/ee_mat_el.f95`, Listing 19) and a module file (`ee/ee.f95`, Listing 20). Finally, the name of the process group needs to be added to the `GROUPS` and `WGROUPS` variables of the makefile.

6.2 Study of ξ_c dependence

When performing calculations with MCMULE, we need to check that the dependence of the unphysical ξ_c parameter introduced in the FKS scheme (cf. Appendix A) actually drops out at NLO and NNLO. In principle it is sufficient to do this once during the development phase. However, we consider it good practice to also do this (albeit with a reduced range of ξ_c) for

```

!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
      MODULE EE_MAT_EL
!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!

use functions
use ee_ee2eel, only: ee2eel
use ee_ee2eeg, only: ee2eeg
implicit none

contains

FUNCTION EE2EE(p1,p2,q1,q2)
  !! e-(p1) e-(p2) -> e-(q1) e-(q2)
  !! for massive electrons
  ...
END FUNCTION EE2EE

FUNCTION EE2EEF(p1,p2,q1,q2)
  !! e-(p1) e-(p2) -> e-(q1) e-(q2)
  !! massive electrons
real(kind=prec) :: p1(4),p2(4),q1(4),q2(4)
real(kind=prec) :: ee2eef, mat0, Epart

Epart = sqrt(sq(p1+p2))
mat0 = ee2ee(p1,p2,q1,q2)

ee2eef = ee2eel(p1,p2,q1,q2) + alpha / (2 * pi) * mat0 * (&
  - Ieik(xieik1,Epart,p1,p2) + Ieik(xieik1,Epart,p1,q1) &
  + Ieik(xieik1,Epart,p1,q2) + Ieik(xieik1,Epart,p2,q1) &
  + Ieik(xieik1,Epart,p2,q2) - Ieik(xieik1,Epart,q1,q2))

END FUNCTION EE2EEF
!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
      END MODULE EE_MAT_EL
!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!

```

Listing 19: The file `ee/ee_mat_el.f95` imports the complicated matrix elements `ee2eel` and `ee2eeg1`, defines the simple matrix element `ee2ee` as per 16, and provides an interface for the $\mathcal{M}_n^{(1)f}$ that is called from integrands.

```

!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
      MODULE EE
!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!

use functions
use phase_space, only: ksoft, ksoftA, ksoftB
use ee_mat_el
implicit none
contains

FUNCTION EE2EEG_S(p1,p2,q1,q2)
  !! e-(p1) e-(p2) --> e-(q1) e-(q2) y(ksoft)
  !! both massive and massless electrons
  real(kind=prec) :: p1(4),p2(4),q1(4),q2(4)
  real(kind=prec) :: ee2eeg_s

  ee2eeg_s = 2 * (- eik(p1,ksoft,p2) + eik(p1,ksoft,q1) &
    + eik(p1,ksoft,q2) + eik(p2,ksoft,q1) &
    + eik(p2,ksoft,q2) - eik(q1,ksoft,q2) &
    ) * ee2ee(p1,p2,q1,q2)
  ee2eeg_s = (4.*pi*alpha) * ee2eeg_s
END FUNCTION EE2EEG_S
!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
      END MODULE EE
!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!

```

Listing 20: The module file ee/ee.f95 which imports all matrix elements of ee_mat_el and defines the soft limits.

production runs.

Because the ξ_c dependence is induced through terms as $\xi_c^{-2\epsilon}/\epsilon$, we know the functional dependence of $\sigma_{n+j}^{(\ell)}$. For example, at NLO we have

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_n^{(1)}(\xi_c) &= a_{0,0} + a_{0,1} \log(\xi_c), \\ \sigma_{n+1}^{(1)}(\xi_c) &= a_{1,0} + a_{1,1} \log(\xi_c),\end{aligned}\tag{18a}$$

where ξ_c independence of $\sigma^{(1)}$ of course requires

$$a_{0,1} + a_{1,1} = 0.\tag{18b}$$

At NNLO we have

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_n^{(2)}(\xi_c) &= a_{0,0} + a_{0,1} \log(\xi_c) + a_{0,2} \log(\xi_c)^2, \\ \sigma_{n+1}^{(2)}(\xi_c) &= a_{1,0} + a_{1,1} \log(\xi_c) + a_{1,2} \log(\xi_c)^2, \\ \sigma_{n+2}^{(2)}(\xi_c) &= a_{2,0} + a_{2,1} \log(\xi_c) + a_{2,2} \log(\xi_c)^2.\end{aligned}\tag{19a}$$

We require

$$a_{0,i} + a_{1,i} + a_{2,i} = 0\tag{19b}$$

for $i = 1, 2$. However, the IR structure allows for an even stronger statement for the $a_{j,2}$ terms

$$a_{0,2} = a_{2,2} = -\frac{a_{1,2}}{2}.\tag{19c}$$

Of course we cannot directly calculate any of the $a_{1,i}$ or $a_{2,i}$ because we use numerical integration to obtain the $\sigma_{n+j}^{(\ell)}$. Still, knowing the coefficients can be extremely helpful when debugging the code or to just quantify how well the ξ_c dependence vanishes. Hence, we use a fitting routine to fit the Monte Carlo results *after* any phase-space partitioning has been undone. Sometimes non of this is sufficient to pin-point the source of a problem to any one integrand. However, if the goodness of, for example, $\sigma_{n+2}^{(2)}(\xi_c)$ is much worse than the one for $\sigma_{n+1}^{(2)}(\xi_c)$, a problem in the double-real corrections can be expected.

6.3 Example calculations in Mathematica

A thorough understanding of one-loop matrix elements is crucial for any higher-order calculation. In MCMULE, one-loop matrix elements either enter as the virtual contribution to NLO corrections or the real-virtual contribution in NNLO calculations. In any case, a fast numerical routine is required that computes the matrix element.

We perform all one-loop calculations in FDF as this is arguably the simplest scheme available. For theoretical background, we refer to [2] and references therein.

We use QGRAF for the diagram generation. Using the in-house Mathematica package `qgraf` we convert QGRAF's output for manipulation with Package-X [32]. This package is available on request through the MMCT

<https://gitlab.com/mule-tools/qgraf>

An example calculation for the one-loop calculation of $\mu \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu} e \gamma$ can be found in Listing 21. Of course this example can be made more efficient by, for example, feeding the minimal amount of algebra to the loop integration routine.

When using `qgraf` for FDF some attention needs to be paid when considering diagrams with closed fermion loops. By default, `qgraf.wl` evaluates these traces in d dimensions. `RunQGraf` has an option to keep this from happening.

There is a subtlety here that only arise for complicated matrix elements. Because the function Package-X uses for box integrals, `ScalarDOIR6`, is so complicated, no native Fortran implementation exists in MCMULE. Instead, we are defaulting to COLLIER [10] and should directly evaluate the finite part of the PVD function above. The same holds true for the more complicated triangle functions. In fact, only the simple `DiscB` and `ScalarCOIR6` are natively implemented without need for external libraries. For any other functions, a judgement call is necessary of whether one should `LoopRefine` the finite part in the first place. In general, if an integral can be written through logarithms and dilogs of simple arguments (resulting in real answers) or `DiscB` and `ScalarCOIR6`, it makes sense to do so. Otherwise, it is often easier to directly link to COLLIER.

6.4 Coding style and best practice

A large-scale code base like MCMULE cannot live without some basic agreements regarding coding style and operational best practice. These range from a (recommended but not enforced) style guide over the management of the git repository to how to best run MCMULE in development scenarios. All aspects have been discussed within the MMCT.

Fortran code in MCMULE is (mostly) written in accordance with the following style guide. If new code is added, compliance would be appreciated but deviation is allowed if necessary. If in doubt, contact any member of the MMCT.

- Indentation width is two spaces. In Vim this could be implemented by adding the following to `.vimrc`

```
autocmd FileType fortran set tabstop=8 softtabstop=0 expandtab
↪ shiftwidth=2 smarttab
```

- Function and subroutine names are in all-upper case.
- A function body is not indented beyond its definition.
- When specifying floating point literals specify the precision when possible, i.e. `1._prec`.
- Integrands should have `ndim` specified.
- Internal functions should be used where available.
- Masses and other kinematic parameters must be calculated in the matrix elements as local variables; using the global parameters `Mm` and `Me` is strictly forbidden.
- These rules also hold for matrix elements.

```

<<qgraf.wl
onshell = {
  p.p -> M^2, q.q -> m^2, p.q -> s/2
};

A0 = (4GF/Sqrt[2]) "diag1"/.RunQGraf[{"mum"},{"nu","elm"},0] //. {
  line[_ , x_] -> x, p1->p, q1->p-q, q2->q, _δZ | δm -> 0
};
A1 = pref /. RunQGraf[{"mum"},{"nu","elm"},1] //. {
  line[_ , x_] -> x, p1->p, q1->p-q, q2->q, _δZ | δm -> 0
};

M0=Block[{Dim=4},Simplify[Contract[
  1/2 Z2[m] Z2[M] FermionSpinSum[
    A0 /. PL -> (1 - Z5 γ5)/2,
    A0 /. PL -> (1 + Z5 γ5)/2
  ]
]] /. onshell]/.{
  Z2[M_] -> 1 + (α/(4π)) (-3/(2ε)-5/2 + 3/2 Log[M^2/Mu^2]),
  Z5      -> 1 - (α/(4π))
};

M1=Block[{Dim=4},Simplify[Contract[
  1/2 FermionSpinSum[
    A1/.γ.k1 -> γ. 4[k1]+I γ5 μ,
    A0
  ]
]] /. onshell /. {
  μ^n_ /; EvenQ[n] -> μ2^(n/2), μ -> 0
} /. {
  4[k1]. 4[k1] -> k1.k1 + μ2, 4[k1] -> k1
}]]];

M1bare = Simplify[KallenExpand[LoopRefine[LoopRelease[
  Pro2LoopIntegrate[
    Coefficient[M1, μ2, 0]/(16 π^2)
  ]
  + μIntegrate[
    Coefficient[M1, μ2, 1]/(64 π^3),
    1
  ],
  onshell
]]] /. e -> Sqrt[4 πα]];

```

Listing 21: An example on how to calculate the renormalised one-loop matrix element for $\mu \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}e$ in FDF.

For python code, i.e. `pymule` as well as the analysis code, PEP8 compliance is strongly encouraged with the exception of E231 (Missing whitespace after `,`, `;`, and `:`), E731 (Do not assign a lambda expression, use a `def`) as well, in justified cases, i.e. if required by the visual layout, E272 (Multiple spaces before keyword), and E131 (Continuation line unaligned for hanging indent).

MCMULE uses two git repositories for version management. One internal repository and one public-facing one. Releasing to the latter is the responsibility of the MMCT after sufficient vetting was performed by squashing commits to avoid the accidental release of embarrassing or wrong code to the public. However, even the internal repository has certain rules attached. In general, developers are encouraged to not commit wrong or unvetted code though this can obviously not be completely avoided in practice. To avoid uncontrollable growth of the git repository, large files movements are strongly discouraged. This also means that matrix elements should not be completely overhauled barring unanimous agreement. Instead, developers are encouraged to add a new matrix element file and link to that instead.

Even when running MCMULE for development purposes the usage of menu files is strongly encouraged because the code will do its utmost to automatically document the run by storing the git version as well as any modification thereof. This allows for easy and unique reconstruction of what was running. For production runs this is not optional; these must be conducted with menu files after which the run folder must be stored with an analysis script and all data on the AFS as well as the user file library to ensure data retention.

A The FKS² scheme

In the following we very briefly review the FKS [26, 27] and FKS² schemes [5] though this is not meant as an introduction into these schemes. For this see [2, 5, 28]. Here, we just give a schematic overview with the basic information required to understand the structure of the code.

The core idea of this method is to render the phase-space integration of a real matrix element finite by subtracting all possible soft limits. The subtracted pieces are partially integrated over the phase space and combined with the virtual matrix elements to form finite integrands.

The NLO corrections $\sigma^{(1)}$ to a cross section are split into a n particle and $(n + 1)$ particle contribution and are written as

$$\sigma^{(1)} = \sigma_n^{(1)}(\xi_c) + \sigma_{n+1}^{(1)}(\xi_c), \quad (20a)$$

$$\sigma_n^{(1)}(\xi_c) = \int d\Phi_n^{d=4} \left(\mathcal{M}_n^{(1)} + \hat{\mathcal{E}}(\xi_c) \mathcal{M}_n^{(0)} \right) = \int d\Phi_n^{d=4} \mathcal{M}_n^{(1)f}, \quad (20b)$$

$$\sigma_{n+1}^{(1)}(\xi_c) = \int d\Phi_{n+1}^{d=4} \left(\frac{1}{\xi_1} \right)_c (\xi_1 \mathcal{M}_{n+1}^{(0)f}). \quad (20c)$$

In (20c), ξ_1 is a variable of the $(n + 1)$ parton phase space $d\Phi_{n+1}^{d=4}$ that corresponds to the (scaled) energy of the emitted photon. For $\xi_1 \rightarrow 0$ the real matrix element $\mathcal{M}_{n+1}^{(0)f}$ develops a singularity. The superscripts (0) and f indicate that the matrix element is computed at tree level and is finite, i.e. free of explicit infrared poles $1/\epsilon$. In order to avoid an implicit infrared pole upon integration, the ξ_1 integration is modified by the factor $\xi_1(1/\xi_1)_c$, where the distribution $(1/\xi_1)_c$ acts on a test function f as

$$\int_0^1 d\xi_1 \left(\frac{1}{\xi_1} \right)_c f(\xi_1) \equiv \int_0^1 d\xi_1 \frac{f(\xi_1) - f(0)\theta(\xi_c - \xi_1)}{\xi_1}. \quad (21)$$

Thus, for $\xi_1 < \xi_c$, the integrand is modified through the subtraction of the soft limit. This renders the integration finite. However, it also modifies the result. The missing piece of the real corrections can be trivially integrated over ξ_1 . This results in the integrated eikonal factor $\hat{\mathcal{E}}(\xi_c)$ times the tree-level matrix element for the n particle process, $\mathcal{M}_n^{(0)}$. The factor $\hat{\mathcal{E}}(\xi_c)$ has an explicit $1/\epsilon$ pole that cancels precisely the corresponding pole in the virtual matrix element $\mathcal{M}_n^{(1)}$. Thus, the combined integrand of (20b) is free of explicit poles, hence denoted by $\mathcal{M}_n^{(1)f}$, and can be integrated numerically over the n particle phase space $d\Phi_n^{d=4}$.

The parameter ξ_c that has been introduced to split the real corrections can be chosen arbitrarily as long as

$$0 < \xi_c \leq \xi_{\max} = 1 - \frac{(\sum_i m_i)^2}{s}, \quad (22)$$

where the sum is over all masses in the final state. The ξ_c dependence has to cancel exactly between (20b) and (20c) since at no point any approximation was made in the integration. Checking this independence is a very useful tool to test the implementation of the method, as well as its numerical stability.

The finite matrix element $\mathcal{M}_n^{(1)f}$ is simply the first-order expansion of the general YFS exponentiation formula for soft singularities

$$e^{\hat{\mathcal{E}}} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{M}_n^{(\ell)} = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{M}_n^{(\ell)f} = \mathcal{M}_n^{(0)} + \left(\mathcal{M}_n^{(1)} + \hat{\mathcal{E}}(\xi_c) \mathcal{M}_n^{(0)} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\alpha^2), \quad (23)$$

where we exploited the implicit factor α in $\hat{\mathcal{E}}$.

For QED with massive fermions this scheme can be extended to NNLO and, in fact beyond. The NNLO corrections are split into three parts

$$\sigma_n^{(2)}(\xi_c) = \int d\Phi_n^{d=4} \left(\mathcal{M}_n^{(2)} + \hat{\mathcal{E}}(\xi_c) \mathcal{M}_n^{(1)} + \frac{1}{2!} \mathcal{M}_n^{(0)} \hat{\mathcal{E}}(\xi_c)^2 \right) = \int d\Phi_n^{d=4} \mathcal{M}_n^{(2)f}, \quad (24a)$$

$$\sigma_{n+1}^{(2)}(\xi_c) = \int d\Phi_{n+1}^{d=4} \left(\frac{1}{\xi_1} \right)_c \left(\xi_1 \mathcal{M}_{n+1}^{(1)f}(\xi_c) \right), \quad (24b)$$

$$\sigma_{n+2}^{(2)}(\xi_c) = \int d\Phi_{n+2}^{d=4} \left(\frac{1}{\xi_1} \right)_c \left(\frac{1}{\xi_2} \right)_c \left(\xi_1 \xi_2 \mathcal{M}_{n+2}^{(0)f} \right). \quad (24c)$$

Thus we have to evaluate n parton contributions, single-subtracted $(n+1)$ parton contributions, and double-subtracted $(n+2)$ parton contributions. This structure will be mirrored in the Fortran code. The ξ_c dependence cancels, once all three contributions are taken into account. For this subtraction method we need the matrix elements with massive fermions. If the two-loop amplitudes are available only for massless fermions, it is possible to use massification [33].

A.1 FKS^ℓ: extension to N^ℓLO

The pattern that has emerged in the previous cases leads to the following extension to an arbitrary order ℓ in perturbation theory:

$$d\sigma^{(\ell)} = \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} d\sigma_{n+j}^{(\ell)}(\xi_c), \quad (25a)$$

$$d\sigma_{n+j}^{(\ell)}(\xi_c) = d\Phi_{n+j}^{d=4} \frac{1}{j!} \left(\prod_{i=1}^j \left(\frac{1}{\xi_i} \right)_c \xi_i \right) \mathcal{M}_{n+j}^{(\ell-j)f}(\xi_c). \quad (25b)$$

The eikonal subtracted matrix elements

$$\mathcal{M}_m^{(\ell)f} = \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \frac{\hat{\mathcal{E}}^j}{j!} \mathcal{M}_m^{(\ell-j)}, \quad (26)$$

(with the special case $\mathcal{M}_m^{(0)f} = \mathcal{M}_m^{(0)}$ included) are free from $1/\epsilon$ poles, as indicated in (23). Furthermore, the phase-space integrations are manifestly finite.

B Available processes and which_pieces

Here we list all generic processes and pieces available in MCMULE. In some cases a generic piece is split into various partitions (cf. Section 5.1 for details on why that is important).

C Particle identification in MCMULE

The following table lists the `which_pieces` of MCMULE as well as the corresponding PID. This information is obtained by compare the entry for a `which_piece` in `src/integrands.f95` with the entry in `src/mat_e1.f95`. For example for `m2ennee0` we find in `integrands`

```

case('m2ennee0')
  call set_func(b'000000', pm2enneeav)
  ps => psd6_23_24_34_e56 ; fxn => sigma_0
  nparticle = 6 ; ndim = 11
  masses(1:6) = (/ Mm, Me, 0._prec, 0._prec, Me, Me /)
  convfac = 0.25/Mm
  polarised = .true.

```

This indicates that the process is available with polarised muons. The masses give a first indication for PID. To narrow this down, we find in `mat_e1` for `pm2enneeav`

```

use mudecrare, only: pm2enneeav!!(p1,n1,p2,qa,qb,p3,p4)
!! mu+(p1) -> e+(p2) \nu_mu(qA) \bar{\nu}_\mu(qB) e+(p4) e-(p3)
!! mu-(p1) -> e-(p2) \bar{\mu}_e(qA) \nu_\tau(qB) e-(p4) e+(p3)

```

This means that $p_1 = p1$, $p_2 = p2$, $p_3 = qa$, $p_4 = qb$, $p_5 = p3$, $p_6 = p4$.

which_piece	P?	p_1	p_2	p_3	p_4	p_5	p_6	p_7
m2enn0								
m2ennF	✓	μ^\pm	\rightarrow	e^\pm	$[\nu\bar{\nu}]$			
m2ennFF								
m5ennR								
m2ennRF								
m2ennG0	✓	μ^\pm	\rightarrow	e^\pm	$[\nu\bar{\nu}]$	γ		
m2ennGV								
m2ennGC								
m2ennRR								
m2ennGR	✓	μ^\pm	\rightarrow	e^\pm	$[\nu\bar{\nu}]$	γ	γ	
m2ennee0								
m2enneeV	✓	μ^\pm	\rightarrow	e^\pm	$[\nu\bar{\nu}]$	e^\mp	e^\pm	
m2enneeC								
m2enneeA								
m2enneeR	✓	μ^\pm	\rightarrow	e^\pm	$[\nu\bar{\nu}]$	e^\mp	e^\pm	γ
tm2ennee0								
tm2enneeV	✓	τ^+	\rightarrow	μ^+	$[\nu\bar{\nu}]$	e^-	e^+	
tm2enneeC								
tm2enneeA								
tm2enneeR	✓	τ^+	\rightarrow	μ^+	$[\nu\bar{\nu}]$	e^-	e^+	γ
m2ej0								
m2ejF	✓	μ^\pm	\rightarrow	e^\pm	J			
m2ejR								
m2ejG0	✓	μ^\pm	\rightarrow	e^\pm	J	γ		

which_piece	P?	p_1	p_2	p_3	p_4	p_5	p_6	p_7
em2em0								
em2emV								
em2emC								
em2emFEE								
em2emFEM								
em2emFMM		e^-	μ^-	\rightarrow	e^-	μ^-		
em2emA								
em2emFFEEEE								
em2emAA								
em2emAFEE								
em2emNFEE								
em2emREE								
em2emREM								
em2emRMM		e^-	μ^-	\rightarrow	e^-	μ^-	γ	
em2emRFEEEE								
em2emAREE								
em2emRREEEE		e^-	μ^-	\rightarrow	e^-	μ^-	γ	γ
mp2mp0								
mp2mpF								
mp2mpA								
mp2mpFF								
mp2mpAA								
mp2mpAF								
mp2mpNF								
mp2mpR								
mp2mpRF		μ^-	p	\rightarrow	μ^-	p	γ	
mp2mpAR								
mp2mpRR		μ^-	p	\rightarrow	μ^-	p	γ	γ
ee2mm0		e^-	e^+	\rightarrow	μ^+	μ^-		
em2emF								
ee2mmR		e^-	e^+	\rightarrow	μ^+	μ^-	γ	
ee2ee0								
ee2eeA								
ee2eeF								
ee2eeFF		e^-	e^-	\rightarrow	e^-	e^-		
ee2eeAA								
ee2eeAF								
ee2eeNF								
ee2eeR								
ee2eeRF		e^-	e^-	\rightarrow	e^-	e^-	γ	
ee2eeAR								
ee2eeRR		e^-	e^-	\rightarrow	e^-	e^-	γ	γ
eb2eb0								
eb2ebF		e^-	e^+	\rightarrow	e^-	e^+		

which_piece	P?	p_1	p_2	p_3	p_4	p_5	p_6	p_7
eb2ebFF								
eb2ebR eb2ebRF		e^-	e^+	\rightarrow	e^-	e^+	γ	
eb2ebRR		e^-	e^+	\rightarrow	e^-	e^+	γ	γ
ee2nn0 ee2nnF ee2nnS ee2nnSS ee2nnCC		e^\pm	e^\mp	\rightarrow	ν	ν		
ee2nnR ee2nnRF ee2nnI		e^\pm	e^\mp	\rightarrow	$[\nu\bar{\nu}]$	γ		
ee2nnRR		e^\pm	e^\mp	\rightarrow	$[\nu\bar{\nu}]$	γ	γ	

D pymule: a reference

We have already encountered `pymule` in Section 3 as the tool of choice to analyse MCMULE results. There we just presented the functions required for an NLO analysis. In this section, we present all functions of `pymule` with examples.

Note that this section assumes a working knowledge of `python`, `numpy`, and to some extent `matplotlib`. All examples use `IPython` as the interpreter with the `%pylab` magic command. All examples below require `pymule` to be loaded.

```
from pymule import *
```

In the following we will perform a step-by-step analysis of μ - e scattering. Note that the analysis is slightly contrived to demonstrate more `pymule` functions than usually necessary. At the end a realistic example is shown. The dataset used here can be obtained from the [user library](#)

```
$ git clone git@gitlab.com:mule-tools/user-library
$ cd user-library/mu-e-scattering/muone-legacy/
$ tar xf em2em_muone_paper/out.tar.bz2
```

In `pymule` data is represented as `numpy` arrays. Numbers are always represented as `np.array([y, \rightarrow e])` and histograms as `np.array([[x1, y1, e1], [x2, y2, e2], ...])`. `pymule` provides some tools to work with these objects as listed below.

D.1 Low-level operations

We begin by loading just a single vegas files, say using the function `importvegas`.

```
importvegas
```

`importvegas(filename="", fp=None)` loads a vegas file, either specified by a filename or a file pointer. The function returns a vegas dictionary containing the following keys

time: the job's run time (since `v2`)

msg: any message. Usually this contains information on the state of the integrator (since `v2`)

SHA: the first 5 characters of the source-tree's SHA1 hash at compile time.

iteration: the number of iterations completed in this file

value: the best estimate for the cross section and its error as `np.array([y, e])`

chi2a: the χ^2 estimate of the integrator

all histograms as specified by their name(..) in `user`

Consider a simple example of $e\mu \rightarrow e\mu$ at LO

```
dat = importvegas('out/em2em0_muone_S0000047404X1.00000D1.00000
↳ _ITMX070x010M_00.vegas')
print conv*alpha**2*dat['value']
# prints [1.21422874e+02 7.04800543e-06]
print dat['chi2a']
# prints 1.11594202899
```

Users who do not wish to use `pymule` for their analysis can at this stage use `numpy` to save histograms into `csv` files for import in other software

```
np.savetxt('thetae.csv', dat['thetae'], delimiter=',')
```

Note that, because of the way histograms are defined in Section 5.4, a histogram can only be generated if the iteration `dat['iteration']` ≥ 2 . Otherwise, the histograms are omitted.

As a next step, we need to be able to merge multiple statistically independent numbers into one result.

mergenumbers

`mergenumbers(values)` statistically combines a list of values with uncertainties. Accepts either a python `list` or a `np.array`. Unless requested otherwise with `quiet=True`, the $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}$ is printed.

Internally, the merging of n values y_i with errors e_i works according to

$$y = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i}{e_i^2} \quad \text{and} \quad e = \sqrt{1/w}$$

with

$$w = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{e_i^2}.$$

For example using `glob` we can find all LO contributions `em2em0`. We load and merge these numbers

```

import glob
data = [importvegas(i)['value'] for i in glob.glob('out/em2em0*')]
print data
# prints [array([5.85594422e-03, 3.12980893e-10]),
#         array([5.85594402e-03, 3.39908979e-10]),
#         array([5.85594395e-03, 3.14824640e-10]),
#         array([5.85594414e-03, 3.24457947e-10])]
xs = mergenumbers(data)
print xs
# prints array([5.85594409e-03, 1.61264817e-10])

```

As discussed before, the χ^2 of this merge is an important quantifier.

chisq

`chisq(values)` calculates the $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}$ of the values in this list. Accepts either a python `list` or a `np.array`.

Using the definitions above, we can find the χ^2 of the combination as

$$\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{y_i - y}{e_i} \right)^2$$

In our case, we write

```

print chisq(data)
# prints 0.11222356647338004

```

We need to be able to do the same for the distributions that we have calculated.

mergeplots

`mergeplots(ps)` statistically combines a list of plots. `mergeplots(ps, returnchi=`
 \rightarrow `True)` also returns the bin-wise χ^2 of the combination.

Let us consider the observable $d\sigma/d\theta_e$ that is coded as `thetae` in user

```

data = [importvegas(i)['thetae'] for i in glob.glob('out/em2em0*')]
thetaE = mergeplots(data)
print thetaE

```

An important consistency check is whether any given histogram such as `thetae` gives the same result as the cross section. For this we have the function `integratehistogram`

integratehistogram

Given a histogram `hist`, `integratehistogram(hist)` returns the integral over this histogram *without* error estimation. This means that `integratehistogram` calculates

$$\int \frac{d\sigma}{dx} dx \approx \Delta \times \sum_{i=0}^{\text{nr_bins}} \text{hist}[i].$$

Let us check the electron distribution `thetae` against the value for the cross section `xs[0]`

```

print integratehistogram(thetaE)/xs[0]

```

The value returned, 0.9999994010342004 indicates very good agreement.

D.2 High-level analysis

The operations above could in principle be used to write a full analysis. However, these steps are easily automated. The globbing, loading, merging, and sorting of data that we have done by hand before is implemented in the function `sigma`, one of `pymule`'s most important functions.

sigma

`sigma` loads multiple `vegas` files, sorts them by their value for ξ_c and merges the random seeds for each value of ξ_c using `mergeseeds`. It returns a dictionary whose keys are tuples `(xinormcut, delcut)` of Table 4. The values of this dictionary are the `vegas` dictionaries obtained after `mergeseeds`, albeit with a reduced list of keys

time: the total run time involved in this dictionary

value: the value obtained from merging the different random seeds

chi2a: a list of the χ^2 from combining the values of the different seeds and a list of the individual χ^2 values of the constituent datasets.

We call this type of dictionary a set.

`sigma(which_piece, ...)` takes a variety of optional arguments that can be overwritten using `setup`

folder: which folder (or tar file) to search for `vegas` files (default: `'.'`)

flavour: the flavour to load (default: everything, i.e. `'.*'`)

obs: the observable to load (the bit after the 0) (default: `''`)

folderp: a regular expression to match directory structures of a tar file (default: everything, i.e. `'.*'`)

filenames: provide a list of file names to consider. Otherwise all files found will be considered, either `os.listdir` or `list(tar)` (default: `None`, implying everything)

merge: given a dictionary of histograms `{'name': n}` merges `n` bins in the histogram name (default: `{}`, i.e. no merging)

types: functions that convert the groups matched by `pattern` into python objects. Common examples would be `int` or `float` (default: `[int, float, float]` as per `MCMULEfilename` convention)

sanitycheck: a function (lambda or named) that, given a `vegas` dictionary, whether to include the file in the output (`return True`) or to skip (`return False`) (default: `lambda x:True`, i.e. include everything)

setup

`setup` specifies the default values used by `sigma`. Note that explicitly provided options in `sigma` take precedence.

For the example, we load the electronic virtual corrections, i.e. `em2emFEE`. Further, we make sure that only datasets enter where the χ^2 of the integration is below 2.

```

setup(folder='em2em_muone_paper/out.tar.bz2')
vdata = sigma('em2emFEE', sanitycheck=lambda dic: dic['chi2a'] < 2)
print vdata.keys()
# [(0.3, 0.3), (1.0, 1.0), (0.5, 0.5), (0.1, 0.1)]
print vdata[(1.,1.)].keys()
# ['chi2a', 'thetae', 'value', 'time', 'tmm', ...]
print vdata[(1.,1.)]['chi2a']
# [0.33193960129511735, [0.7844202898550725, 0.8414855072463768]]

```

Note that `sigma` returns an empty dictionary `{}` if it cannot find any file matching the request. Further, histograms are only included if all files loaded contain the same histograms. When we go to NLO, we also have to merge all different values of ξ_c . This is automatised in `pymule`

mergefks

`mergefks` is arguably one of most important function in `pymule` because it performs the FKS merge, i.e. it takes random-seed-merged results (usually from `sigma`) and produces a final set, containing cross sections, distributions, and run-time information. The `'chi2a'` return is a list of the following

- the χ^2 of the FKS merge
- a list of χ^2 from previous operations, such as random seed merging or the integration.

`mergefks` has an optional argument `anyxi` (or anything starting with `anyxi` such as `anyxi2`) for ξ_c -independent results such as an explicit one-loop run `em2emV` or more often the VP contribution.

We often also appropriate `mergefks` for the LO import. Hence, the full import is

```

setup(obs='0')
lodata = mergefks(sigma('em2em0'))
nlodata = mergefks(
    sigma('em2emFEE'), sigma('em2emFEM'), sigma('em2emFMM'),
    sigma('em2emREE15'), sigma('em2emREE35'),
    sigma('em2emREM'), sigma('em2emRMM'),
    anyxi=sigma('em2emA', obs='2')
)

```

Note that we have used `obs='2'` for `em2emA` which includes the full VP contributions. Now that we have our dataset, we need to attach the correct power of α to the cross section and the distributions. For this we use `scaleset`

scaleset

`scaleset(s, v)` rescales the cross section and distributions of the set `s`. Note that this naturally changes the cross section.

We multiply the full dataset with the correct factors of α and the conversion factor `conv = (c \hbar)2`

```

lodata = scaleset(lodata, alpha**2*conv)
nlodata = scaleset(nlodata, alpha**3*conv)

```

Now that we have the NLO corrections $\sigma^{(1)}$, we want to add it to the LO to obtain the full NLO prediction σ_1 . Let us begin with the cross section

plusnumbers
`plusnumbers([y1, e1], [y2, e2], ...)` adds the numbers `y1` etc. and returns

$$\left[y1 + y2 + \dots, \sqrt{e1^2 + e2^2 + \dots} \right]$$

for the value and error estimate.

```
nloXS = plusnumbers(lodata['value'], nloata['value'])
```

Next we calculate the K factor $K = \sigma_1/\sigma_0$.

dividenumbers
`dividenumbers([y1, e1], [y2, e2])` divides the numbers `y1/y2` and returns

$$\left[\frac{y1}{y2}, \sqrt{\frac{e2^2 y1^2}{y2^4} + \frac{e1^2}{y2^2}} \right]$$

for the value and error estimate.

timesnumbers
`times([y1, e1], [y2, e2])` multiplies the numbers `y1` and `y2` and returns

$$\left[y1 \cdot y2, \sqrt{y2^2 e1^2 + y1^2 e2^2} \right]$$

for the value and error estimate.

In our case, we will divide `nloXS` by `lodata['value']`

```
Kfac = dividenumbers(nloXS, lodata['value'])
```

D.3 Visualisation

Now that we have calculated these results, we may want to print the cross section. Of course `print Kfac` is possible. Hence, `printnumber` exists purely for convenience.

printnumber
`printnumber(x)` returns a string representation of the number `x` with uncertainties to one significant digits.

In our case we can print the K factor as

```
print printnumber(Kfac)
# 1.0043028(1)
```

Now that we have loaded all relevant datasets, let us visualise the results. We begin by simply plotting $d\sigma/d\theta_e$ at LO.

errorband

`errorband(p, ...)` plots an error band of a compatible histogram. The input histogram `p` must be formatted according to standard as `np.array([[x1, y1, e1], [x2 ↪ , y2, e2], ...])` `errorband` takes some optional arguments

ax: the axes object to plot. If not specified `gca()` is used, potentially creating a new axes

col: a `matplotlib` colour specification. Per default `matplotlib` decides using the order specified in `pymule.colours`

underflow, overflow: whether and how big to plot under- and overflow bins. Either logical or numbers indicating how much bigger the under- and overflow bins shall be (default: `False`)

Here, we will not focus on the details of `matplotlib` and instead only briefly show a few useful commands. The following creates a figure object, plots the LO data with certain bounds and adds labels.

```
fig = figure()
errorband(lodata['thetae'])
xlim(0, 0.022)
xlabel('$\\theta_e$, /\\, {\\rm\\_rad}$')
ylabel('$\\D\\sigma/\\D\\theta_e$')
fig.savefig('ee.pdf')
```

The plot, we have generated above has one major flaw. The electron's angle is more conveniently expressed in mrad. We would want to change the histogram in such a way that does not influence the integral over the histogram.

scaleplot

`scaleplot(a, s)` rescales a plot by `s` such that the integrated plot remains unchanged, i.e. it rescales x and y as $x \rightarrow x/s$ and $y \rightarrow y s$. This is useful to, for example, change units.

`scaleplot(a, sx, sy)` rescales the x and y axis independently of each other with $x \rightarrow x/s_x$ and $y \rightarrow y s_y$.

In our case, we write

```
fig = figure()
errorband(scaleplot(lodata['thetae'], 1e-3))
ylim(0, 11) ; xlim(0, 22)
xlabel('$\\theta_e$, /\\, {\\rm\\_mrad}$')
ylabel('$\\D\\sigma/\\D\\theta_e$')
```

Even though this plot is fine, we may want to merge a number of bins into one larger bin. Reasons for this might be aesthetics, putting emphasise on the fact that we show a histogram, or error reduction.

mergebins

`mergebins(p, n)` merges `n` adjacent bins in the histogram `p` into one larger bin, reducing the uncertainty. This processes loses `len(p) % n` bins at the end of the histogram.

Let us merge 10 bins in the example above

```
errorband(mergebins(scaleplot(lodata['thetae'],1e-3),5))
```

We now want to calculate the full NLO prediction $d\sigma_1/d\theta_e$ and the K factor.

addplot

`addplots(a, b, sa=1., sb=1.)` add the plots `a` and `b`, weighted by `sa` and `sb`, i.e. it returns

$$sa\ a + sb\ b.$$

For example, use `addplots(a, b, sb=-1)` to calculate $a - b$.

divideplots

`divideplots(a, b, offset=0.)` divides the plots `a` and `b`, off-setted by `offset`, i.e. it returns $a/b + offset$. `offset=1.` is useful for K factors.

```
thetaL0 = lodata['thetae']
thetaNLO = addplots(thetaL0, nldata['thetae'])
# These two lines are equivalent
thetaK = divideplots(thetaNLO, thetaL0)
thetaK = divideplots(nldata['thetae'], lodata['thetae'], offset
    ↪ =1.)
```

Ideally we should plot the K factor and $d\sigma/d\theta_e$ in the same plot. The MCMULE way of doing this is using `twopanel` with the NLO prediction in the upper of two panels and the K in the lower.

twopanel

`twopanel(...)` creates two panel plot, accommodating at most four axes (upper left, upper right, lower left, and lower right). The x axis is naturally shared.

labelx: label for the x axis (default: "")

upleft: data plotted in the upper-left axes, either `np.array` (single plot) or list of plots (default: nothing shown)

labupleft: label for the upper-left y axis (default: "")

colupleft: colour for upper-left data. Must at least as long as `upleft` (default: default colour scheme `pymule.colours.defcol`)

downleft, labdownleft, coldownleft: similar for lower-left axes

upright, labupright, colupright: similar for upper-right axes

downright, labdownright, coldownright: similar for lower-right axes

upalign, downalign: values that should be aligned on the left and right y axis in the upper or lower panel.

If some dataset is missing, nothing is shown for that axes and the axes is not created. `twopanel` returns the figure created as well as a list of axes created.

threepanel

threepanel works similar with labelx, upleft, labupleft, colupleft, middleleft, labmiddleleft, colmiddleleft, downleft, labdownleft, and coldownleft.

Would we use NNLO data here, $K^{(2)}$ would be plotted on the right-axis of the lower panel. Here we instead plot the NLO corrections split into purely electronic corrections and everything else (cf. [1, 34, 35] for why this makes sense). As a first step we need to load the appropriate data

```
nldataEE = scaleset(mergefks(
    sigma('em2emFEE'), sigma('em2emREE15'), sigma('em2emREE35')
), alpha**3*conv)
nldataMM = scaleset(mergefks(
    sigma('em2emFMM'), sigma('em2emRMM')
), alpha**3*conv)
nldataEM = scaleset(mergefks(
    sigma('em2emFEM'), sigma('em2emREM')
), alpha**3*conv)
```

Next, we can plot the data using twopanel. We adapt the bounds assign axis labels and colours in the same call but adapt the bounds in a second step.

```
from pymule.plot import twopanel
fig, (ax1, ax2, ax3) = twopanel(
    labelx='$\\theta_e\\,/\\,\\{\\rm\\_rad}\\$',
    upleft=thetaNLO, labupleft="$\\D\\sigma/\\D\\_\\theta_e$",
    downleft=divideplots(nldataEE['thetae'], thetaLO, offset=1),
    labdownleft="$K^{(1)}_e$", coldownleft='C0',
    downright=[
        divideplots(nldataMM['thetae'], thetaLO, offset=1),
        divideplots(nldataEM['thetae'], thetaLO, offset=1)
    ],
    labdownright="$K^{(1)}_{\\mu,m}$",
    coldownright=['C0', 'C1']
)
ax1.set_xlim(-0.001, 0.024)
ax2.set_ylim(0.7, 1.3)
ax3.set_ylim(0.99, 1.01)
```

Plotting results like this can be rather repetitive. For convenience, we hence provide a function kplot that provides plots of this form automatically.

kplot

`kplot(sigma, ...)` produces a K -factor plot in line with MCMULE's design, i.e. a two-panel plot showing in the upper panel the cross sections and in the lower panel the K -factor defined as

$$K^{(i)} = d\sigma^{(i)}/d\sigma^{(i-1)} \quad (27)$$

The data to plot, `sigma`, is given as a dictionary with keys "lo", "nlo", and possibly " \leftrightarrow nnlo". Note that `kplot` only takes the corrections at a loop order, not the full distribution. The keys "nlo2" and "nnlo2" are optional and will be drawn dashed in the lower panel.

`labelx`: the label for the x axis

`labelsigma`: the label for the upper y axis

`labelknlo` (`labelknnlo`: the labels for the K factors (default (per design guidelines) $\delta K^{(1)}$ and $\delta K^{(2)}$)

`show`, `showk`: a list which cross sections and K -factors to show (if available), 0 indicates the LO cross section, 1 the NLO etc. -1 indicates the last given cross section

`legend`: a dictionary with the legend for "lo", "nlo", and "nnlo".

`legendopts`: a `kwargs` dictionary of options to be passed to `legend(..)` as well as the "what"-key indicating whether the legend such be placed in the lower panel (1, default), upper panel (u), or as a `figlegend` (fig). Notable is the "loc"-key that places the legend inside the object specified by "what". Possible values are (cf. `matplotlib`'s `legend`): 'upper_right', 'upper_left', 'lower_left', 'lower_right', 'right', 'center_left', 'center_right', 'lower_center', ' \leftrightarrow upper_center', and 'center'

`nomule`: if set to `True`, no mule will be printed

`kplot` returns the figure as well as all axis created. All labels support \LaTeX in-line maths.

We perform this at NNLO. For this, we need the corresponding MCMULE dataset where we only include electronic corrections

```
nnlodata = scaleset(mergefks(
    sigma('em2emFFEEEE'),
    sigma('em2emRFEEEE15'), sigma('em2emRFEEEE35'),
    sigma('em2emRREEEEE1516'), sigma('em2emRREEEEE3536'),
    sigma('em2emAFEE', obs='0'),
    sigma('em2emAREE15', obs='0'), sigma('em2emAREE35', obs='0'),
    anyxi1=sigma('em2emNFEE', obs='0'),
    anyxi2=sigma('em2emAA', obs='0')
), alpha**4*conv)
```

Next, we use `kplot` to plot the LO and NNLO cross sections σ_0 and σ_2 . There is no point in plotting σ_1 due to the smallness of $\sigma^{(2)}$. In the K -factor panel we plot $\delta K = K - 1$ as per MCMULE standard, both at NLO and NNLO.

```
fig, (ax1, ax2, ax3) = kplot(
    {
        'lo': mergebins(scaleplot(lodata['thetae'], 1e-3)[:221], 4),
        'nlo': mergebins(scaleplot(nlodata['thetae'], 1e-3)[:221], 4),
        'nnlo': mergebins(scaleplot(nnlodata['thetae'], 1e-3)[:221], 4)
    },
    labelx="$\\theta_e\\,/\\,{\\rm\\_\\mu\\rad}\\$",
    labelsigma="$\\D\\sigma/\\D\\theta_e\\_\\_\\_\\{\\rm\\upmu\\_b}\\$",
    legend={
        'lo': '$\\sigma^{(0)}$',
        'nlo': '$\\sigma^{(1)}$',
        'nnlo': '$\\sigma^{(2)}$'
    },
    legendopts={'what': 'u', 'loc': 'lower\\_right'}
)
```

D.4 Saving results

After a successful analysis we might want to store the result in a format that can be processed outside of `pymule`. For this we need to add all contributions.

addsets

`addsets(s)` adds a list of sets (cross section, histograms, and run time). The `'chi2a'` is a list of constituent χ^2 values.

We use `addsets` to add the LO, NLO, and NNLO contributions into one set

```
fulldata = addsets([lodata, nlodata, nnlodata])
print "Total\\_cross\\_section:\\_" + printnumbers(fulldata['value'])
```

Maybe we now want to store the result in a machine-readable. Given that we already have the `vegas` file standard, this seems like a good choice, especially for internal sharing.

exportvegas

`exportvegas(dic, filename="", fp=None)` saves a vegas dictionary or set to a vegas file, either specified by a filename or a file pointer. The set may contain the following keys

time: the job's run time (default: CPU time since the start of the executing process, `time.clock()`)

msg: any message (default: `"Warning: Generated with Python"`)

SHA: the first five byte of a SHA1 hash of the state of the file (default: `'00000'`)

iteration: the number of iterations completed in this file (default: 2, making sure that $1/(it - 1)$ in various estimates are well-defined)

value: the best estimate for the cross section and its error as `np.array([y, e])`

chi2a: the χ^2 estimate of the integrator

all histograms as specified by their `name(..)` in `user`

We save our result in a file `muone.vegas` as well as `csv` file that can be easily shared with other collaboratio

```
exportvegas(fulldata, 'muone.vegas')
np.savetxt('muone-thetae.csv', fulldata['thetae'], delimiter=',')
```

D.5 Internal functions

The following functions are exposed by `pymule` but it is somewhat unlikely that a user would have to call them directly. Hence their description is kept brief.

importreg

`importreg(r, ...)` imports all `vegas` files matching the regular expression `r` and returns a dictionary containing the results, keyed with the groups defined in `r`. It takes a subset of the optional arguments defined for `sigma`: `folder`, `filenames`, `merge`, `types`, `sanitycheck`.

pattern

`pattern(...)` constructs a regular expression to be used in `importreg` matching the usual MCMULE file name convention. It takes the following optional arguments

`piece`: the `which_piece` to load (default: everything, i.e. `"*"`)

`flavour`: the flavour to load (default: everything, i.e. `"*"`)

`obs`: the observable to load (the bit after the 0) (default: `''`)

`folderp`: a regular expression to match directory structures of a tar file (default: everything, i.e. `"*"`)

and uses it to construct the following regular expression

```
# with obs
folderp + piece + '_' + flavour + '_S(\d+)X([\d\.]+)D([\d
  ↪ \.]+).*0' + obs + '.vegas'
# without obs
folderp + piece + '_' + flavour + '_S(\d+)X([\d\.]+)D([\d
  ↪ \.]+).*'
```

mergeset

`mergeset` statistically merges a set of runs, combining cross sections, histograms, and run-time information. The `'chi2a'` of the output is a list of

- the χ^2 of the cross section combination and
- a list of the individual χ^2 values.

mergeseeds

`mergeseeds(s, key)` statistically merges the random seeds of a set of runs using `mergeset`. The key is used to group runs in the set `s`. Usually, this refers to the FKS parameters (in the default notation `lambda x: (x[1], x[2])` referring to ξ_c (`x ↪ [1]`) and δ (`x[2]`)).

combineplots

`combineplots(a, b, yfunc, efunc, tol=1e-8)` combines the plots `a` and `b`, assuming a function for the values (`yfunc`) and the errors (`efunc`). Users will not likely call this directly.

`tol` is the number of digits the `x` values have to agree at to considered equal.

combineNplots

Given a combination function (such as `addplots`) and a list of plots, this returns

```
func(plots[0], func(plots[1], func(plots[2], ...)))
```

This is useful to, for example, add a number of plots as `combineNplots(addplots, ↪ plots)`

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